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TOOLKIT ON SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

DESCRIPTION

Social entrepreneurship is an approach by individuals, groups, start-up companies or entrepreneurs, in which they develop, fund and implement solutions to social, cultural, or environmental issues.

EnMind Consortium

Social Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurial mindset for future youth work

Cooperation for innovation and exchange of good practices

Strategic Partnerships in the field of youth

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IO1 – Toolkit on social entrepreneurship

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Abstract	<p>Social entrepreneurship matters for numerous reasons and plays a key role nowadays. Social entrepreneurship supports people who are marginalised or who find themselves in unjust positions due to events that are beyond their control. A social entrepreneur differs from a typical entrepreneur in that, whereas the traditional entrepreneur's ultimate purpose is to make money, the social entrepreneur's ultimate goal is to make long-term societal change.</p> <p>This course is intended to provide the tips and tricks necessary to start a business from the scratch. Trainees are taught not only how to conceptualize their business idea clearly, but how to plan and execute it. They gain knowledge about strategies to develop their business model, ways to analyse it and sources of financing for start-ups. Moreover, they become aware of globally widespread problems that people are facing and the imperative need to solve them. Furthermore, once they have their business, trainees are taught about the importance of measuring their performance and strategies to do it.</p> <p>Those competences will provide the necessary information in order to develop soft skills associated with social entrepreneurship. The outcome will be a citizen with the set of knowledge, traits, behaviours, skills and mindset of a social entrepreneur.</p>

Keywords	Social entrepreneurship, business idea, social business model canvas, SOAR, SWOT, elevator pitch, marketing, performance indicators.
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Summary

The purpose of this toolkit is to assist youth workers, trainers and educators to introduce and organize new training courses and enhance the existing training materials, to further deliver effective training to youth in the field of social entrepreneurship.

This support tool comprises a set of approaches and methodologies that can be used in Europe to support young people, particularly NEETs and disadvantaged young people, who would like to start a business in the social entrepreneurship field. The toolkit is designed as an accessible document giving a course of action for the experts on how to intercept, involve, activate and train disadvantaged young people.

In order to have a full understanding of the topic as well as to improve the competences of youth workers, trainers and educators to organize and deliver the course in the online environment, the content has been structured as follows:

- Module 1. Social entrepreneurship
- Module 2. Sustainable Development Goals
- Module 3. Impact of social entrepreneurship on society
- Module 4. Creating social enterprises
- Module 5. Business idea
- Module 6. SOAR analysis for creating a value proposition
- Module 7. Business models
- Module 8. Social business models
- Module 9. Pitch your business
- Module 10. Funding opportunities
- Module 11. Measuring performance
- Module 12. Marketing strategies

The above modules contain the knowledge that the expert needs, in order to have adequate preparation for the development of a business, with a particular focus on social entrepreneurship (e.g. Business Model Canvas development, marketing strategies, what is a social enterprise).

Being aware that the success of the training depends to a great extent on the educational environment, each module illustrates the techniques and methodologies of approach to the learners, according to the specificities of the target group (young people, NEET, new graduates, immigrants).

Nevertheless, the training tools are essential to reach the course objectives and to enable the achievement of the learning outcomes. The authors proposed a set of useful tools for the expert to provide training on the social entrepreneurship topic. These tools range from classic training tools to multimedia ones, all being intended to adapt the course to the needs and specificities of the target group.

Finally, the youth workers, trainers and educators will be able to understand how to introduce young people in an innovative way to European policies and the mechanisms that lead to their training, help them develop an entrepreneurial idea and know the existing tools to put it into practice.

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Module 1. Social entrepreneurship

Introduction

In this module, trainers will be able to acquire knowledge on the concepts of social entrepreneurship and social economy, analysing also the main features of a social entrepreneur and the differences between a social entrepreneur an intrapreneur and an innovator. To this aim, the following topics will be focused on:

- Entrepreneur
- Intrapreneur
- Innovator
- What is the social economy?
- Social venture
- Social innovation
- Social impact
- Triple Bottom Line (People, Profit Planet)
- Social entrepreneur

Competences

This section will enable the learners to:

- Highlighting the definition of social entrepreneurship, and social economy
- Assessing what it takes to become a social entrepreneur
- Outlining the difference between a social entrepreneur, intrapreneur and innovator

Duration

The module will last 4.5 hours including the three workshops proposed. In the theory section, there are explanations of the basic concepts of social entrepreneurship and social economy with a focus on the figures of social entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs. The practical part will allow learners to engage in interactive workshops to get more familiar with the difference between entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship, with the different types of sectors where a social enterprise can be launched and which characteristics a social entrepreneur should have.

This module is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and videos to watch.

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneur

An entrepreneur is an individual who creates a new business, bearing most of the **risks** and enjoying most of the rewards. The entrepreneur is commonly seen as an innovator, a source of new ideas, goods, services, and business/or procedures.

Entrepreneurship is one of the resources economists categorize as integral to production, the other three being land/natural resources, labour and capital. An entrepreneur combines the first three of these to manufacture goods or provide services. They typically create a business plan, hire labour, acquire resources and financing, and provide leadership and management for the business.

An entrepreneur is a **starter**. An entrepreneur is an initiator, a challenger and a driver. Someone that creates something new, either an initiative, a business or a company. He or she is the beginning (and sometimes the end) of a venture, project or activity. The entrepreneur might not be the ideator, but he or she is definitely the one that decides to make that idea a reality.

An entrepreneur is the **driver**. The entrepreneur is the person in charge, the leader and the person to look to for leadership. He or she is the one that pushes forward and inspires a team to follow. The entrepreneur is the one that sits in the driver's seat and has the ability to change direction, accelerate, slow down or even stop a venture.

An entrepreneur is **accountable** and responsible. Entrepreneurs are the people responsible for the destiny of their venture, which can be a company, a project, or any other endeavour. The entrepreneur is the one that has the highest stakes in the venture, thus the one that needs to be empowered to fully direct the endeavour.

Qualities of an entrepreneur:

- Be open-minded
- Problem identifier and solver
- Passionate
- Confident and disciplined
- Risk-taker
- A constant flow of ideas
- Creative
- Competitive
- Opportunist
- Determination (Strong-willed)

„Entrepreneurship is a calling, not a Job“ Steve Blank

The major types of *entrepreneurs* include; **social entrepreneurs**, **serial entrepreneurs**, and *lifestyle entrepreneurs*. We would like to focus our attention on the Social Entrepreneur.

Who is the social entrepreneur

A social entrepreneur is a person who pursues novel applications that have the potential to solve community-based problems. These individuals are willing to take on the risk and effort to create positive changes in society through their initiatives.

Widespread use of ethical practices such as impact investing, conscious consumerism, and corporate social responsibility programs facilitate the success of social entrepreneurs.

Difference between innovator and entrepreneur

Entrepreneurs are individuals who are focused primarily on **creating a business** and increasing shareholder value. While the business may be centred around a specific product or service, entrepreneurs want to be able to take the start-up that they've created and form it into a successful business that can stand beside the leaders of the industry. As such, entrepreneurs will usually know more about marketing a product to investors and prospective customers than they do about creating and developing a product.

An entrepreneur will also work to identify and develop customer **networks** that can be effectively monetized and determine what **market** can be reached with the product or service in question. Entrepreneurs usually create companies surrounding the product that they want to place on the market, which is why most individuals who create start-ups are considered to be entrepreneurs.

In order for an entrepreneur to be successful, the main characteristics that they will need to have to include being passionate, hard-working, flexible, and forward-thinking. Entrepreneurs will need to be able to adapt to changes in the market.

An **inventor** is someone who invents a product and is simply looking to create a new product that has never before been made. In most cases, an inventor isn't trying to place this invention on the market.

An **innovator** can create new ideas, methods, or products. These individuals might also develop **new iterations** of products that have already been created. While the product or service will have already been invented, an innovator will be able to improve or make some kind of significant contribution to the invention.

An example of innovation is the development of the laptop computer. Even though the computer had already been invented, the innovation of the computer allowed it to be transformed into a portable device that could be carried around. If you believe that you can improve on a product that's already on the market and make it more appealing to prospective customers, you would classify as an innovator.

There are many characteristics that an innovator will need to be successful. The mark of a great innovator is being able to anticipate a need that the market is about to have. Innovations are typically created by taking advantage of emerging technologies and capturing trends at the moment they start. Innovators are highly productive individuals who are passionate, willing to take risks, and want to push the envelope.

Intrapreneur

The term **intrapreneurship** refers to a system that allows an employee to act like an entrepreneur within a company or other organization. An intrapreneurship creates an entrepreneurial environment by allowing employees to use their entrepreneurial skills for the benefit of both the company and the employee. It gives employees the freedom to experiment, as well as the potential for growth within an organization. Intrapreneurship fosters autonomy and independence while attempting to find the best resolution.

The concept of "intrapreneurship" was not born in 1978 when students Gifford and Elizabeth Pinchot, while attending the School for Entrepreneurs in Tarrytown (New York), wrote a sort of paper with their reflections on the intra-corporate entrepreneur. A few years later, in 1985, the economist Norman Macrae in an article for the Economist, credited Gifford Pinchot as the inventor of the word "intrapreneur".

Who is the intrapreneur

An intrapreneur is an employee who is tasked with developing an **innovative idea** or **project** within a company. The intrapreneur may not face the outsized risks or reap the outsized rewards of an entrepreneur. However, the intrapreneur has access to the resources and capabilities of an established company.

Intrapreneurs are self-motivated, proactive, and action-oriented people who take the initiative to pursue an innovative product or service.

Intrapreneurs can develop and use their creativity to enhance **existing** goods and services within the context of the business, all without any of the risks attached to being an entrepreneur. Using these skills as part of a team lets the intrapreneur test theories and determine which methods are most effective for solving problems.

One important difference between intrapreneurs and entrepreneurs is that intrapreneurs are tasked with using the company's resources, while entrepreneurs use their own.

An entrepreneur starts a company as a means of providing a good or service. An intrapreneur seeks to improve the performance of an existing company.

Inevitably, as an intrapreneur develops the skills needed to recognize and solve important problems, that intrapreneur may turn into an entrepreneur therefore intrapreneurship is one step toward entrepreneurship.

Qualities of an intrapreneur

Employers need to recognize these employees because it can help the company to lead to innovation and growth.

Identifying intrapreneurs can sometimes be difficult. These employees are generally **self-starters** who are both ambitious and goal-oriented. They are often able to solve problems on their own and come up with ideas that lead to process improvements. An intrapreneur may also take certain risks by assuming multiple tasks—even some that he or she may not be comfortable with—and look for new challenges.

Intrapreneurs are able to resolve specific issues such as increasing productivity or cutting costs. This requires a **high level of skill**—namely leadership skills and thinking outside the box—directly applicable to the assignment. An intrapreneur also **takes risks** and drives innovation within a business to better serve the market through increased goods and services.

A successful intrapreneur is comfortable being uncomfortable while testing his or her ideas until achieving the desired results. He or she is also able to interpret trends in the marketplace and visualize how the company needs to evolve to stay ahead of its competition. The intrapreneur is part of a company's backbone and the driving force mapping out the organization's future.

The 10 commandments of the intrapreneur (by Gifford Pinchot)

- 1) Build your team, intrapreneuring is not a solo activity.
- 2) Share credit widely.
- 3) Ask for advice before you ask for resources.
- 4) Underpromise and overdeliver — publicity triggers the corporate immune system.
- 5) Do any job needed to make your dream work, regardless of your job description.
- 6) Remember it is easier to ask for forgiveness than for permission.
- 7) Keep the best interests of the company and its customers in mind, especially when you have to bend the rules or circumvent the bureaucracy.
- 8) Come to work each day willing to be fired.
- 9) Be true to your goals, but be realistic about how to achieve them.
- 10) Honour and educate your sponsors

Social entrepreneurship

Social intrapreneur

A specific category of intrapreneur that is emerging is that of the social intrapreneurs, who add to all those characteristics we have previously identified (focus on objectives, strong motivation, planning, etc.), wanting to achieve objectives that have a positive **social impact** and they want to do it together with the company they work for, as company involvement is part of the positive impact.

Understanding social entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship is a way of doing business that is connected to a desire for social change. What distinguishes it from entrepreneurship in the strict sense is the fact that the main objective of a social entrepreneur is not only the achievement of profit but the implementation of solutions that lead to an improvement in the **quality of life** for as many people as possible.

The social enterprise is based on the same business model as a traditional company, but its strategies revolve around the solution of a **social problem**.

The social economy is intended to make **profits for people** other than investors or owners; in other words, it aims to serve the members and not to obtain a return on investment as the traditional mainstream capital companies do. The social economy includes cooperatives, mutual societies, non-profit associations, foundations and social enterprises.

The European Commission considers a social enterprise an operator in the social economy whose main objective is to have a social, societal or environmental impact rather than make a profit for the investors or owners. It operates by providing products and services for the market in an entrepreneurial and innovative way and the profits are mainly reinvested to achieve social objectives. It is managed in an open and responsible manner, in accordance with the principle of solidarity and mutuality by involving employees, consumers and investors affected by its commercial activities.

The Commission uses the term 'social enterprise' to cover the following types of business

- Those for who the social or societal objective of the common good is the reason for the commercial activity, often in the form of a high level of social innovation
- Those whose profits are mainly reinvested to achieve this social objective
- Those where the method of organisation or the ownership system reflects the enterprise's mission, using democratic or participatory principles or focusing on social justice

There is no single legal form for social enterprises. Many social enterprises operate in the form of social cooperatives, some are registered as private companies limited by guarantee, some are mutual, and a lot of them are non-profit-distributing organisations like provident societies, associations, voluntary organisations, charities or foundations.

In Europe, there are 2 million social economy enterprises, mostly micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), representing 10% of all businesses in the EU, and more than 11 million people (about 6% of the EU's employees) work in these enterprises and up to 160 million people in Europe are members of social economy enterprises. Thus, they have an essential role in the EU's employment, social cohesion, regional and rural development, environmental protection, consumer protection, agricultural, third countries development, and social security policies.

Across Europe, we can find different legal forms and a wide range of products and services. Many social enterprises operate in the form of social cooperatives, some are registered as private companies limited by guarantee, some are mutual, and many are non-profit-distributing organizations like provident societies, associations, voluntary organisations, charities or foundations.

Despite their diversity, social enterprises mainly operate in the following fields:

- Work integration – training and integration of people with disabilities and unemployed people;
- Personal social services – health, well-being and medical care, professional training, education, health services, childcare services, services for elderly people, or aid for disadvantaged people;

- Local development of disadvantaged areas – social enterprises in remote rural areas, neighbourhood development/rehabilitation schemes in urban areas, development aid and development cooperation with third countries;
- Other – including recycling, environmental protection, sports, arts, culture or historical preservation, science, research and innovation, consumer protection and amateur sports.

The concept of social entrepreneurship can take on different declinations and characteristics depending on the country being considered. While maintaining the basic characteristics inherent in the purpose and purposes unchanged.

Social Economy

Traditionally, the European social model has always been characterized by the prominent role played by a variety of organisations that differ both from private corporations and public institutions.

These are private organisations that typically pursue goals other than profit: their main purpose is not to generate financial gains for their owners or stakeholders but to provide goods and services either to their members or to the community at large.

These organisations, which have been active in Europe for nearly two centuries, have been recognized and regulated in many countries through specific legal forms (including the cooperative, the mutual, and the association), have set up their own representative organisations to interact with public authorities, and have contributed in various ways to the social and economic development of our continent. The label that is used, in the tradition of many European countries and recently also by the EU, to refer to these organisations is the ‘social economy’ – a term that stresses the special attention that these organisations pay to the social consequences of their activities, and their participative governance structures.

What distinguishes social enterprises from traditional associations or charities is the fact that social enterprises earn a substantial proportion of their income through trading, rather than being dependent on grants or donations.

What is the social economy

Social economics is a branch of economics—and social science—that focuses on the relationship between **social behaviour** and **economics**. Social economics consists of two broad perspectives that, though opposite in their approach, can be thought of as complementary.

The first, pioneered by Nobelist Gary Becker, applies the basic theoretical and applied tools of neoclassical microeconomics to areas of human behaviour not traditionally considered part of economics proper, such as crime and punishment, drug abuse, marriage, and family decisions.

The second perspective applies the ideas of other social sciences, such as sociology, psychology, and identity group studies to subjects of an economic nature like consumer behaviour or labour markets. These practitioners of social economics use history, current events, politics, and other social sciences to predict social trends that could potentially impact the economy.

Triple bottom line

The theories of social economics often consider factors that are outside the focus of mainstream economics, including the effect of the environment and ecology on consumption and wealth.

Social economics is primarily concerned with the **interplay between social processes and economic activity within a society**. Social economics may attempt to explain how a particular social group or socioeconomic class behaves within a society, including their actions as consumers.

Sustainability project management: The TBL – Triple Bottom Line

Source: [Research Gate](#)

Traditionally, business leaders concerned themselves with their bottom lines—or, the monetary profits their businesses made. Today, more leaders have begun to think sustainably. The triple bottom line theory expands the traditional accounting framework to include two other performance areas: the **social** and **environmental** impacts of companies.

These three bottom lines are often referred to as the three P's: **people**, **planet**, and **profit**.

The triple bottom line is a sustainability-based accounting method that focuses on people, profit and planet. The triple bottom line differs from traditional reporting frameworks because it includes ecological and social aspects that are often difficult to measure. The idea is that by improving in any one sector, you'll improve the company overall.

People

This bottom line measures businesses' impact on human capital. A company using the triple bottom line has a responsibility to not only shareholders but also employees, vendors, customers, the community where it does business and anyone else impacted by the organization, whether directly or indirectly. It recognizes the interdependency of all the human relationships and interactions that enable the company to operate. This can translate into actions such as providing quality healthcare

benefits and flexible work schedules to employees, offering opportunities for professional or educational advancement, creating a safe work environment, and engaging in fair labour practices.

Planet

Companies following the TBL model work to reduce their ecological footprint. They recognize that the smaller the environmental impact a company has, the longer it can operate. At its most basic level, this involves not producing products that are unsafe or unhealthy for the planet and the people on it, but it also includes reducing consumption, waste and emissions. It involves specific actions, such as using renewable energy sources, reducing energy use, disposing of toxic materials safely and adopting a host of green corporate policies.

Profit

All companies are concerned about their financial standing, but businesses committed to the triple bottom line look at profits in terms of not just what they can do for shareholders, but also how they can help the broader community. In this model, a company helps stimulate economic growth and create wealth by compensating employees fairly, supporting local suppliers with its business, generating innovation, and paying its fair share of taxes. It also makes financially prudent but ethically driven decisions about how and where to source materials, products or labour.

On its own, the triple bottom line is simply a reporting tool, so it isn't going to improve society or protect the environment. It can drive change, though, because both people and the planet benefit when a company decides to adopt a socially responsible model.

Examples of companies using the TBL approach can be found at www.business.com/articles/triple-bottom-line-defined/

Workshop: Types of entrepreneurs

In this activity, participants will be able to deepen their knowledge of the different types of social entrepreneurs and reflect on the characteristics identified as the most valuable and essential that in their opinion social entrepreneurs should embody.

Purpose

To identify the characteristics of different entrepreneurs and reflect on the ideal type of entrepreneur.

Time

1 hour

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

Participants, divided into small groups (suggested number 5 groups)

Objectives

To improve the entrepreneurship skills of participants

To clarify that different types of entrepreneurs have good and bad traits

Materials

- 5 papers with 5 types of entrepreneurs for each group.
- Small pieces of paper: stars, squares, rounds, rectangles, triangles.

Facilitation steps

- 1) Introduction: In the introduction, the facilitator should explain the whole activity.
- 2) Method: cut from the paper: stars, squares, rounds, rectangles, and triangles. Put all the figures into an envelope (or some bag). Then each member chooses the figure from the envelope. Members with the same figures create a team. Should be 5 teams, because of the 5 types of entrepreneurs which will be discussed.
- 3) Each team receives a paper with a type of entrepreneur and a description of it. During this time, each group has to discuss the type of entrepreneur their received. Also, each group should prepare acting during which they will present their type of entrepreneur (basically they have to concentrate on the characteristics of each type). Also, each team has to prepare a short explanation of what type of entrepreneur they had presented.
- 4) Each group has 3min for acting/presenting.
- 5) Debate/discuss each group's performance and particular types of entrepreneurs. After each team's acting, the facilitator of the activity should ask other teams what characteristics they have noticed and do they think that it is a good or bad type of entrepreneur. After a short discussion, the acting team should say what type they have presented and read the description they have received from the facilitator before the team works. And also, shortly explain the description, and how they understand it.

Methods

Group activity

Reflection

Debriefing

Have you ever had experience with any of these types of entrepreneurs?

Have you ever acted like one of them?

How do you think which type of entrepreneur could be the most successful one and which the least?

References

Handouts:

- 1) **The sceptical entrepreneur** - This entrepreneur sees the success of others and immediately starts to question it. They examine that person's business and look for the "lucky" breaks, or inheritance they think that successful entrepreneur received. Maybe it's the news or previous life experiences, but they are sceptical of success and don't believe it's possible without all the stars falling into place. When you can't see or believe success is possible, you'll never get to a place in your mind that allows you to take action. You will stay stuck; you'll make every excuse and believe it because of your sceptical mindset. This is the scariest type of entrepreneur.
- 2) **The copycat entrepreneur** - This entrepreneur sees the success of others and tries to copy them exactly. Their website is the same, their business cards are the same, and the way they present themselves is the carbon copy of a leader in their industry. Take Pat Flynn from the popular blog Smart Passive Income. Since Pat became popular, there has been a whole wave of people that copy him line-for-line. There is nothing wrong with modelling success—it's actually very smart. There is a fine line, however, between modelling and copying. Modelling success means you see what works and figure out how to make it relevant to your business, and who you are as a person. If you have been copying, get honest and switch from copying to modelling.

- 3) **The research entrepreneur** - This entrepreneur loves to learn. They research every possible scenario and outcome for strategies to start or grow a business. There is nothing wrong with learning, but when that's all you do, it becomes a problem. The research ends up becoming an excuse for not taking action. While you should always strive to learn what works, and what could help your business, you have to implement. Most entrepreneurs know more than they think; too many entrepreneurs fall victim to information overload. The key to success is learning and then implementing. The implementation has to happen.
- 4) **The determined entrepreneur** - This entrepreneur hasn't "made it" but they will, no matter what. They see the value in entrepreneurship, they see that success is possible without copying, and they do everything they can to start or grow their business. Starting and growing a business is hard, and it takes time, but there is proof that it's possible to thrive. To get there, you need to change your mindset from focusing on what too many people consider "reality" to what you know your reality can be. Successful entrepreneurs have determination as their backstory.
- 5) **The accomplished entrepreneur** - This entrepreneur has gone through all the stages of entrepreneurship and building a business and has reached success. They are now focused on scaling their business and leaving a legacy that extends beyond their lifetime. The accomplished entrepreneur has figured out the things that will help you reach success. They have figured out how to connect with their customer and how to solve their biggest struggles. They will never "make it" but they are experiencing true freedom. They understand their time is their most valuable resource so they use it wisely.

Other useful resources:

YEAST Toolkit https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1604/YEST_Toolbox.pdf

Workshops about social entrepreneurship

https://ied.eu/entre_files/outcomes/Workshops_about_social_entrepreneurship.pdf

Workshop: Differences between social entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship

Purpose

To provide a deeper understanding of social entrepreneurship and the difference between entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship to increase participants' communication and team working skills.

Time

1.5 hours

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

Objectives

Make participants able to identify and clarify the main differences between entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship.

Materials

- Red papers with vulnerable name groups, e.g. elderly, women head of family, poor people, etc.

- Yellow papers with labour sector names, e.g. Technology, Food, Health, etc.
- Papers and pencils.
- Handout for participants: Definitions
- Classroom/training room with chairs

Facilitation steps

The facilitator divides the participants in groups.

Introduction on Entrepreneurship and Social Entrepreneurship (10 min) The moderator/tutor gives to the participants a small definition of what are Social Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurship. He/she can leave the definitions written on the board.

Practical exercise: Vulnerable groups and labour market opportunities (50 min). Introduction on vulnerable groups. The trainer should lead the discussion in plenary on the topic: What does it mean to be a vulnerable group in society, and how they are defined?

Participants should be invited to give examples of vulnerable groups. If they don't have many ideas, the trainer should give several typical examples. (15min)

Instructions

The group will sit down in a circle around the moderator/tutor, who will give each participant one of the red cards with the name of a vulnerable group and one yellow card with the name of a labour sector. (5min)

Individual reflection

Each participant has ten minutes to think about an idea for a Social Entrepreneurship proposal using the group and sector given. (10 min)

Presentation

Each participant explains in max. 3 min. the proposal and the tutor as well as the other participants can make comments and suggestions if there is a need (20min)

Methods

Group activity

Reflection

Debriefing

Do you think that you also possess the qualities that you wrote on your posters?

Do you think that these attitudes and qualities can be obtained by learning or by experience?

Do you think that there is only one model of the perfect entrepreneur or there can be more of them?

Do you think that these attitudes and qualities depend on the field where the entrepreneur would like to develop his business?

References

Handouts

Definition of entrepreneurship

The capacity and willingness to develop, organize and manage a business venture along with any of its risks in order to make a profit. The most obvious example of entrepreneurship is the starting of new

businesses. In economics, entrepreneurship combined with land, labour, natural resources and capital can produce profit. An entrepreneurial spirit is characterized by innovation and risk-taking and is an essential part of a nation's ability to succeed in an ever-changing and increasingly competitive global marketplace. (Business Dictionary: Entrepreneurship, available at: <http://bit.ly/1wTC9G8>)

The basic entrepreneurship definition is the act of creating a business or businesses while building and scaling it to generate a profit. However, entrepreneurship is also about transforming the world by solving big problems. Like initiating social change, creating an innovative product or presenting a new life-changing solution. It can even help lower unemployment rates through job creation to help reduce poverty. Entrepreneurship is what people do to take their career and dreams into their hands and lead it in the direction of their own choice. It's about building a life on your own terms. No bosses. No restricting schedules. And no one holding you back. Entrepreneurs are able to take the first step into making the world a better place, for everyone in it. (Oberlo: "What is Entrepreneurship? Entrepreneur Definition and Meaning" <http://bit.ly/2Cpn0nS>)

Definition of social entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship is the idea of combining innovative methods used by business entrepreneurs with a desire to bring about significant social change. Social entrepreneurs address pervasive social problems, find ways to overcome them, and implement their solutions, ideally on a large scale. Just like a regular business entrepreneur, a social entrepreneur must take risks and be determined in order for his or her social venture to be successful. (IO1)

Social entrepreneurship is, at its most basic level, doing business for a social cause. It might also be referred to as altruistic entrepreneurship.

Social entrepreneurs combine commerce and social issues in a way that improves the lives of people connected to the cause. They don't measure their success in terms of profit alone – success to social entrepreneurs means that they have improved the world, however, they define that. (Shopify: What is Social Entrepreneurship? <http://bit.ly/2BSwPtI>)

Social entrepreneurship is all about recognizing social problems and achieving social change by employing entrepreneurial principles, processes and operations. It is all about making research to completely define a particular social problem and then organizing, creating and managing a social venture to attain the desired change. The change may or may not include a thorough elimination of a social problem. It may be a lifetime process focusing on the improvement of the existing circumstances. (Management study guide: What is Social Entrepreneurship? <http://bit.ly/2EWg8vS>)

Other useful resources:

Entrepreneur handbook: What is entrepreneurship? Available at: <http://bit.ly/2CLL7sm>

Harvard business review: Entrepreneurship: A Working Definition <http://bit.ly/1tA1xPz>

EC and OECD: Policy Brief on Women's Entrepreneurship <http://www.oecd.org/cfe/smes/Policy-Brief-on-Women-sEntrepreneurship.pdf>

OECD: Inclusive Entrepreneurship in Europe: Policy briefs <http://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/inclusive-entrepreneurs-in-europe.htm>

Duke Innovation and Entrepreneurship: "Meaning of "Social Entrepreneurship"
<http://bit.ly/1QmW1cc>

Social Entrepreneurship: Definition and Boundaries (Technology Innovation Management Review, February 2012) <http://bit.ly/2FwY9wV>

INVESTOPEDIA: Social Entrepreneur <http://bit.ly/2FxxPTr>

The balance: American Social Entrepreneurs from the 19th Century to the 21st

<http://bit.ly/2GMm6Qk>

Workshop: Types and sectors of social entrepreneurship

This activity involves participants in deepening the social entrepreneurship definition by analyzing different types of sectors where a social enterprise can be launched.

Purpose

To increase the level of knowledge of participants related to existing types and sectors where Social Entrepreneurship is developed.

To visualize in real life how Social Entrepreneurship can be applied.

Time

1.5 hours

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

Objectives

Identify existing types and sectors suitable for Social Entrepreneurship.

Visualize in real life how Social Entrepreneurship can be applied.

Materials

- Classroom/training room
- Cardboards (min. 50cm X 70cm)
- Markers, crayons, coloured pencils
- Sheets blogs; Pencils
- Participant names on pieces of paper and a bag
- Face paintings. Clothes to dress up. Instruments
- Handout: Definitions of the Types of SE printed on individual papers one for each team

Facilitation steps

Intro (10 min)

Divide the group into five small teams, giving to each team a “Type of Social Entrepreneurship*.”

Group work and presentation (65 min)

Each team has to read the definition and example and find a creative way to expose it to the rest of the group. The teams can do any kind of presentation: songs, theatre presentations, drawings, etc. (30 min)

Each team will have 5 minutes to do their exposition. Presentation time includes a couple of minutes breaks between groups (40 min)

Sum-up and theoretical input (15 min)

The trainer and the participants will use this time to clarify the concept and ask questions. The trainer will present selected resources important for this topic

Methods

Group activity

Reflection

Debriefing

In which sectors would you expect to find examples of social entrepreneurship?

References

Types of Social Entrepreneurship <http://bit.ly/2GNg6H6>

Social Enterprise & Entrepreneurship (SEE) Northern Region Partnership
<https://seethechange.ca/about/>

COMMUNITY PROJECT

A community project is a term applied to any community-based project or initiative. This covers a wide variety of different areas within a community or a group. Projects can cover almost anything that concerns the community and aims to address a social, environmental or economic issue.

Examples

- Paquataskamik Project, Fort Albany First Nation is a community-based research and learning initiative aimed at fostering inter-generational dialogue and understanding about the importance of traditional territory to social, cultural and economic well-being. The project involves the ongoing development of a community process bringing together youth, adults and elders.
- Timmins Community Gardens, Timmins are parcels of land divided into small plots to provide residents with access to fresh produce, support nutritional health, strengthen neighbourhood connections, promote sustainability, and increase physical activity in the community. "The garden"s is a volunteer project created through a collaborative partnership of the United Way, Timmins Economic Development Corporation, The Anti-Hunger Coalition, Timmins Family Health Team, The Porcupine Health Unit, The Mountjoy Farmers' Market, Mattagami Region Conservation Authority and individuals from the community.

NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS

A non-profit organization (NPO) is an incorporated organization which exists for educational or charitable reasons, and from which its shareholders do not benefit financially. Surplus revenues are reinvested in the organization to achieve its goals and used for its own expenses, operations, and programs.

In order to reduce dependency on traditional sources of funding and revenue, non-profits are financing their sustainability through a mix of revenue sources that include for-profit businesses, such as local thrift stores.

Examples:

- La Maison Verte, Hearst is owned by the non-profit Association Parmi-Elles, a group of women whose objective since the early 1980s has been to set up business ventures that create jobs for women. Over the years, has contributed greatly to the regional economy through the production of tree seedlings for reforestation and the supply of fresh produce to local markets.
- Thinking Rock Community Arts, Sault Ste. Marie invites communities to share the stories and histories of rural and First Nations communities within the Algoma Region through collective,

multidisciplinary and cross-cultural community arts projects. Thinking Rock accomplishes this by supporting young people to co-create the communities they want to live in and consulting for businesses and community groups.

CO-OPERATIVE

Co-operatives (or “co-ops”) are community-focused businesses that balance people, planet and profit. Co-ops are legally incorporated organizations owned by their members who use their services or purchase their products. Co-ops can provide virtually any product or service and can be either non-profit or for-profit enterprises. The cooperative sector keeps dollars circulating within the local economy, provides secure employment and is a means to revitalize and sustain healthy communities.

Examples:

- Cloverbelt Local Food Co-op, Dryden aims to strengthen food security by encouraging diverse local food production, thereby enhancing overall rural sustainability. This cooperative is unique in that it uses an online platform to connect producers and consumers from a multitude of remote and rural communities in Northern Ontario.
- Eat Local Sudbury, Sudbury a grocery store and distributor that connects eaters with producers. The store primarily sells products from farms within a 150 miles radius of Sudbury, and secondly from the rest of Ontario. The coop serves as a hub for area consumers and producers. Eat Local Sudbury exists to serve its members and to support and promote local food.

SOCIAL ENTERPRISE

A social enterprise, typically initiated by a non-profit, uses business operations and strategies to generate revenue from the private market to assist in sustaining the organization’s primary services.

Different forms of Social Enterprise can include:

- Training for those with challenges in facing the workforce Employment creation for marginalized populations,
- Non-profits that house social enterprises intending to subsidize their services,
- Non-profit/private sector business partnerships that support the goals of the non-profit Businesses owned and operated by Indigenous communities

Examples:

- Roots to Harvest (Urban Youth Garden), Thunder Bay's mission is to provide transformative educational opportunities for youth to engage with local agriculture and cultivate healthy communities. They have a vision of a future where youth are leaders, connecting a diverse community and cultivating food that’s healthy and accessible.
- Soogoma Industries Recycling Depot, Sault Ste. Marie is an arm of Community Living Algoma (a not-for-profit that offers services for adults with developmental disabilities). Soogoma hires CLA clients who would otherwise face barriers to employment. Recycling services provided to the community generate revenue, which is then invested back into Soogoma operations.

SOCIAL PURPOSE BUSINESS

A social purpose business is a profit-making enterprise that also has a positive social and/or environmental impact. Another way to describe a social purpose business refers to having a blended value or triple bottom line: people, planet, profit.

Examples:

- Tidy & Clean Housekeeping Service, Thunder Bay is an environmentally friendly housekeeping service that strictly uses certified Eco-friendly cleaning products as well as products made from recycled materials that are made in Canada!
- The Great Spirit Circle Trail, Manitoulin Island offers nature-based and cultural tourism from an Aboriginal perspective on beautiful, majestic Manitoulin Island and the Sagamok region of North-eastern Ontario, Canada. Tours are hosted by Aboriginal people who have carefully planned itineraries that offer a true reflection of the history and culture of the region and its original inhabitants – the Ojibwe, Odawa and Pottawatomi peoples.

Other useful resources

CDA: Different types of Social Enterprises www.cwcdca.co.uk/Social-enterprise/Different-types-of-Social-Enterprises

Future Learn: Types of social enterprise <https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/social-enterprise-business-doing-good/0/steps/17178>

Conscious Company Media: 6+ types of social enterprise <https://consciouscompanymedia.com/sustainable-business/strategy-models/actually-6-types-social-enterprise/>

Workshops about social entrepreneurship https://ied.eu/entre_files/outcomes/Workshops_about_social_entrepreneurship.pdf

Case study: La Locanda del Giullare social enterprise

"La Locanda del Giullare" - Let's tear down the wall of prejudice with taste.

The city of Trani is full of restaurants, but is there one where you don't eat only food? Now yes and it's called "[La Locanda del Giullare](#)". In the kitchen all the good of inclusion because the restaurant is managed by people with disabilities and social frailties. A team of twenty highly qualified young people who bring traditional Apulian cuisine to the table with passion, enthusiasm, commitment and a great desire to change the world.

They not only strive to bring good food to the table but also take care of the show, art and entertainment to transform every meal into a unique and unforgettable experience.

Task: Read their story and think about this initiative, pros, and cons, similar enterprises.

Resources

Further reading

Social economy and social entrepreneurship – Publications office of the European Union:

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/cc9e291c-517c-4c64-9f29-428b34aea56d>

Blank, S. (2018). The Difference Between Innovators and Entrepreneurs. ThinkGrowth.

<https://thinkgrowth.org/the-difference-between-innovators-and-entrepreneurs-a430602ff8ea>

Social economy in the EU. (n.d.). European Commission. ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/social-economy_en

Video materials

Entrepreneurship is a calling, by Steve Blank: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=peX6wNbZrgQ>

League of Intrapreneurs - What exactly is a social intrapreneur, and why are they so vital to the future of business and our planet: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e3Lz61D2Z14>

Supporting entrepreneurs and the self-employed - The Better Entrepreneurship Policy Tool:

<https://audiovisual.ec.europa.eu/en/video/l-162837>

Bruce Poon Tip "Beyond the Triple Bottom Line" - A new perspective includes in the three P's passion and purpose as fundamental elements to allow the Triple bottom line model to evolve and achieve sustainability: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xbeUftMoFUQ>

Module 2. Sustainable Development Goals

Introduction

In this module, trainers will be able to acquire knowledge of the concepts of sustainable development goals. To this aim, the following topics will be focused on:

- What is sustainable development?
- The Sustainable Development Goals SDGs
- The Covid-19 response

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to:

- Identifying the Sustainable Developments Goals
- Defining sustainable development
- Reflecting on the importance of SDG after the pandemic crisis

Duration

The module will last 1,5 hours including all activities. In the theory section, there are explanations of the basic concepts of Sustainable Development Goals SDGs what they are and how are linked to our current reality.

This module is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and videos to watch.

Sustainable development

There is no doubt that we need to reset the direction of the world economy, from one of widening inequalities, social exclusion, and massive environmental threats to the course of sustainable development.

In September 2015, 193 countries came together at the United Nations to adopt and commit to a long-term, comprehensive strategy to tackle the world's greatest challenges related to global sustainable development. The result was the SDGs, a list of 17 goals to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all by 2030.

All member states of the United Nations have agreed to adopt **“Transforming the World: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development”**.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is a universal action plan for global cooperation on sustainable development for the period 2015 to 2030 that has defined 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with 169 targets.

“This Agenda is a plan of action for people, planet and prosperity. It also seeks to strengthen universal peace in larger freedom, we recognize that eradicating poverty in all its forms and dimensions, including extreme poverty, is the greatest global challenge and an indispensable requirement for sustainable development.”

What is sustainable development?

Sustainable development has been defined as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”.

There are four dimensions to sustainable development – society, environment, culture and economy – which are intertwined, not separate. Sustainability is a paradigm for thinking about the future in which environmental, societal and economic considerations are balanced in the pursuit of improved quality of life. For example, a prosperous society relies on a healthy environment to provide food and resources, safe drinking water and clean air for its citizens.

Eradicating poverty in all its forms and dimensions is an indispensable requirement for sustainable development. To this end, there must be a promotion of sustainable, inclusive and equitable economic growth, creating greater opportunities for all, reducing inequalities, raising basic standards of living, fostering equitable social development and inclusion, and promoting integrated and sustainable management of natural resources and ecosystems.

One might ask, what is the difference between sustainable development and sustainability? Sustainability is often thought of as a long-term goal (i.e. a more sustainable world), while sustainable development refers to the many processes and pathways to achieve it (e.g. sustainable agriculture and forestry, sustainable production and consumption, good government, research and technology transfer, education and training, etc.).

Sustainable development calls for concerted efforts towards building an inclusive, sustainable and resilient future for people and planet.

For sustainable development to be achieved, it is crucial to harmonize three core elements: economic growth, social inclusion and environmental protection. These elements are interconnected and all are crucial for the well-being of individuals and societies.

Implementation and success of the SDGs – Sustainable Development Goals will rely on countries’ own sustainable development policies, plans and programmes, and will be led by countries. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) will be a compass for aligning countries’ plans with their global commitments.

Understanding Sustainable Development Goals

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or Global Goals are a collection of **17 interlinked goals** designed to be a "blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all"

The 17 Goals were adopted by all UN Member States in 2015, as part of the **2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development** which set out a 15-year plan to achieve the Goals.

The Sustainable Development Goals are a call for action by all countries – poor, rich and middle-income – to promote prosperity while protecting the planet. They recognize that ending poverty must go hand-in-hand with strategies that build economic growth and address a range of social needs including education, health, social protection, and job opportunities while tackling climate change and environmental protection. More important than ever, the goals provide a critical framework for COVID-19 recovery. The 17 SDGs are:

- 1) No Poverty
- 2) Zero Hunger
- 3) Good Health and Well-being

- 4) Quality Education
- 5) Gender Equality
- 6) Clean Water and Sanitation
- 7) Affordable and Clean Energy
- 8) Decent Work and Economic Growth
- 9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
- 10) Reducing Inequality
- 11) Sustainable Cities and Communities
- 12) Responsible Consumption and Production
- 13) Climate Action
- 14) Life Below Water
- 15) Life On Land
- 16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions
- 17) Partnerships for the Goals.

The COVID response

“We need to turn the recovery into a real opportunity to do things right for the future.” – UN Secretary-General António Guterres

COVID-19 is spreading human suffering, destabilizing the global economy and upending the lives of billions of people around the globe. Leveraging this moment of crisis, when usual policies and social norms have been disrupted, bold steps can steer the world back on track towards Sustainable Development Goals. This is the time for change, for a profound systemic shift to a more sustainable economy that works for both people and the planet. Unfortunately, COVID-19 is by no means a “silver lining” for the environment.

Visible, positive impacts – whether through improved air quality or reduced greenhouse gas emissions – are but temporary, because they come on the back of tragic economic slowdown and human distress. The pandemic will also result in an increase in the amount of medical and hazardous waste generated. Any positive environmental impact in the wake of this pandemic must therefore be in our changing our production and consumption habits towards cleaner and greener.

Humanity’s expansion on the terrestrial earth’s surface means that today, human activity has altered almost 75 per cent of the earth’s surface, squeezing wildlife and nature into an ever-smaller corner of the planet. And yet, nature is critical to our own survival: therefore, the solution is Building a ‘different economy’.

To support the poorest and most vulnerable, the UN has issued a Framework for the immediate socio-economic response to COVID-19, calling for an extraordinary scale-up of international support and political commitment to ensure that people everywhere have access to essential services and social protection. COVID is More than a health crisis.

Workshop: Words salad

This workshop is a game created to involve team members on different topics about ecology and young entrepreneurship. In fact, participants get to describe terms and concepts related to the themes while having fun. Promotes efficient teamwork to be more competitive with the other teams whilst at the same time learning from the other teams' mistakes or good practices. It also helps to be more tolerant of other team members if there is any kind of miscommunication which might lead to failure.

Purpose

To link ecology and sustainability to social entrepreneurship

To practice teamwork and communication skills

Time

60 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

20 participants

Objectives

Improve the communication skills of participants

Improve training ecology and entrepreneurship concepts in a non-formal way

Make people active and creative

Promote Teamwork

Materials

- Papers
- Scissors
- Pens
- Bowl
- Timer
- Scoreboard

Facilitation steps

Split the group into three or four smaller groups of even numbers.

The smaller groups form a circle around a table or on the floor.

Participants sitting opposite each other are teammates.

The trainers write some cards with words related to ecology and entrepreneurship (e.g. solar panel, tree, start-up etc.) and put them in a bowl in the centre of the table

Each participant gets 1 minute to pick words from the bowl and describe them to his teammate. This is done in three rounds (using the same words each round):

Rounds

1st round: Describe with words but without using the word.

2nd round: Describe using only ONE word.

3rd round: Describe without using words (mime, use of props etc)

Points system: Winning team is the one with the most guessed words. If a word is taking too long or the other person is not getting it, you can pick a different card. The round finishes when the bowl is empty.

Methods

Group activity

Reflection

Debriefing

How could this activity be useful for entrepreneurs in market research and/or marketing?

References

Workshops about social entrepreneurship:

https://ied.eu/entre_files/outcomes/Workshops_about_social_entrepreneurship.pdf

Resources

Further reading

A/RES/70/1 - Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. (2015.). Sustainable Development Goals.

<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/index.php?page=view&type=111&nr=8496&menu=35>

A UN framework for the immediate socio-economic response to COVID-19. (2020). United Nations.

https://www.undp.org/kyrgyzstan/publications/un-framework-immediate-socio-economic-response-covid-19?c_src=CENTRAL&c_src2=GSR

Take Action for the Sustainable Development Goals. (n.d.). Sustainable Development Goals.

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

Video materials

Action that United Nations Development Programme - UNPD will undertake to face this Development crisis <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wqhksKloplo>

Do you know all 17 SDGs? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0XTBYMfZyrM>

Business and sustainable development – can they work for each other?

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rht4d4GdYbM>

Module 3. Impact of social entrepreneurship on society

Introduction

In this module, youth workers will be supported to learn how to develop problem-solving and creativity skills so that learners can reframe problems as opportunities through Impact Gaps Canvas. To this aim, the following topics will be focused on:

- Impacts of Social Enterprises
- Introduction to Impact Gaps Canvas
- How to apply Impact Gaps Canvas
- How to define a measurable impact of a social enterprise

Competences

This section will enable the learners to:

- Explain the social impacts created by social enterprises
- Define the purpose of Impact Gaps Canvas
- Tell how to identify a problem that needs to be met
- Design and apply Impact Gaps Canvas tasks
- Show learners how to reframe problems and challenges as opportunities to create value and social impact
- Guide learners on how to write a precise 10-word impact statement

The youth workers will facilitate the acquisition and improvement of the following entrepreneurial competences.

- Communication
- Critical thinking
- Collaboration
- Creativity
- Goal setting
- Analytical
- Problem-solving
- Decision-making
- Planning

Duration

The module will last 2 hours including all activities. In the theory section, there are examples of businesses that create social impact and Impact Gaps Canvas as a mapping tool to help those who wish to be a change-maker and consider an entrepreneurial path.

This module is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises. Learners will have access to educational materials and practical tasks about Impact Gaps Canvas which lasts 60 minutes.

What value and impact can a social enterprise create

Like many businesses, social enterprises also try to sell products and services to make a profit. In order to make a profit and sustain the enterprise, social entrepreneurs should be clear about what value and

impact they bring to the community. What makes a social enterprise different from any other business is the value they create through many versatile ways:

- Use the profit to do social and environmental good.
- Maximize advancements in human and environmental well-being.
- Use of business technologies and resources to find solutions to social problems.

The impact is also a key element in a social enterprise. Through the value of a social enterprise, an impact can occur as a result of the sale of the product and/or service.

Social enterprises can create the following impacts:

- Create new job opportunities
- Increase the employability of young people by sharing knowledge with them
- Contribute to the economic development of deprived communities.
- Use part of their profits to pay for the needs of disadvantaged individuals (buying shoes, clothes, support for meals)
- Provide equitable opportunities for the disadvantaged.

Here are some examples of businesses that create social impact:

So, how are you going to explore the impact area of your social business create in the community? You can use Impact Gaps Canvas to identify the problem, proposed solutions and actions to date.

[Beauty from Ashes](#) **from Romania** is an attempt to alleviate the trauma suffered by young people over 18 who leave the child protection system through separation from the natural family and institutionalization. The young women involved in the social enterprise work manually to design and make handmade greeting cards made for different occasions. The skills acquired in the workshop are of major importance in the process of integration and learning the skills of independent living. The handmade products obtained are distributed in the country and abroad, on various occasions, and their value is returned in the form of donations to the organization to support the implementation of social projects.

[Çöp\(m\)adam](#) **from Turkey** is questioning what is worth saving or not, çöp(m)adam started as an experimental project in Ayvalık addressing the issues of women's employment in Turkey and the importance of recycling/re-using. çöp(m)adam aims to utilize waste in a creative, aesthetically and unique way. Çöp(m)adam items are produced from the packaging that would be or has been thrown away, by women who have never previously earned a salary. All the products are one-of-a-kind and signed by their producer.

[PizzAut](#) **from Italy** is the first pizzeria run by autistic kids. The project was born from the idea of starting a social inclusion laboratory through the creation of a pizzeria run by young people with autism, supported by catering and rehabilitation professionals.

After the first training phase, which allows them to study the most appropriate job for each of them together with psychologists and educators, the youngsters are included in the PizzAut staff.

The idea came in 2017, Nico Acampora, the father of an autistic child who, seeing his little son playing making pizza, thought that cooking could really engage older autistic children. The boys start training courses, then the first evenings arrive in which they put themselves to the test by cooking for different events.

[Association for Helping the Disabled "Siedlisko"](#) **from Poland** is operating in the town of Staniszcze Wielkie in the Opolskie Voivodeship. As part of its business activity, since 2015, "Siedlisko" has been

running a 24-hour nursing home - it was established to create jobs for people with disabilities who very skilfully perform caring activities and establish positive relationships with seniors.

Large profits are also generated by gastronomic activities conducted by "Siedlisko" - including catering services. The generated profit allows for social activity. The association also implements diagnostic and training projects, as well as offering high-quality health and care services.

The Big Issue from the UK: this is a street newspaper, founded in 1991, that offers homeless people, or individuals at risk of homelessness, the opportunity to earn an income through selling a magazine to the public. Vendors buy The Big Issue magazine for £1.25 and sell it for £2.50, meaning each seller is a micro-entrepreneur who is working, not begging.

Specialisterne from Denmark: trains people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) to meet the requirements of the business sector. Specialisterne also provides a working environment where it is 'normal' to have ASD and where the role of the management and staff is to create the best possible working environment for the employees with ASD. Employees work as business consultants on tasks such as software testing, programming and data entry for the public and private sectors. Specialisterne is active in Europe (Denmark, Austria, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Spain), Australia, Canada, Brazil, USA and Singapore.

Impact gaps canvas

The Impact Gaps Canvas is a mapping tool to help those who wish to be a change-maker and consider an entrepreneurial path. The canvas encourages change makers to take a systems-led leadership approach for designing their careers and initiatives, which requires making decisions about personal or organizational social impact strategy based on understanding the systems within which people work and then envisioning wider system change goals. **The Impact Gaps Canvas is not about trying to solve the problem but identifying the area to contribute and create social impact, unlike Business Model Canvas which is likely to lock people into "one" problem and keep them from exploring the problem the wider system in-depth.**

Source: tacklingheropreneurship.com

Unlike Business Model Canvas, it helps to understand the landscape of the problem by mapping out two parts of the ecosystem and identifying the “gaps” or the possible paths to increase impact.

This tool can be used in a variety of ways like in the application process or initial programming of a social entrepreneurship accelerator program.

Source: tacklingheropreneurship.com

As a tool for educators to help students identify high-impact career paths, class projects in high schools, in community organisations. It is adaptable to a wide variety of contexts since at its core, it asks to do three things:

- explain the facts they know or questions they have about the challenge,
- explain the facts they know or questions they have about the landscape of current solutions,
- explain the gaps they have identified through their research

Impact Gaps Canvas invites users to map two parts of the ecosystem and then identify gaps or possible paths to increase impact. To this aim, the Impact Gaps Canvas encourages the users to understand their chosen challenge through the following parts.

On the **left**, is a list of questions to help them map the ecosystem of a challenge: the numbers, causes, impacts, what is holding the challenge in place, who benefits from the current status quo, and the history and future of the challenge

On the **right**, map the landscape of current solutions: what is already being tried, what resources are available which could be brought to bear in support of an improved network of solutions, what is being tried locally, and what tangential global efforts can be learned from.

In the **centre**, analyse their learning and identify impact gaps: overlooked areas with opportunity for increased impact, key lessons learned from other efforts which could be used to increase the impact of the collective, ideas for changes or new efforts which could link up government, business, non-profit, or individual impacts.

Source: tacklingheropreneurship.com

Workshop: Impact gaps canvas

Purpose

Teach learners how to use Impact Gaps Canvas to solve a challenge or problem.

Time

50 Minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young people, entrepreneurs

Objectives

Enable learners to brainstorm about social problems and think about related solutions

Materials

- Blank Impact Gaps Canvas
- Internet
- Board

Facilitation steps

Before starting the session

Introduce the Canvas and its background, for this you can use the video prepared by Daniella Papi-Thorns.

Then, show the learners the Canvas and give an overview with requirements and questions for the parts to be completed through research and discussions.

Before starting to fill out each part, brainstorm with the learners about the problems and challenges to which they want to address and make a social change. During the brainstorming, write problem or challenge areas on the board. Taking into consideration the specified problems/challenges, create working groups in which the learners will work on similar problems.

During the session

Introduce Challenge Mapping and encourage the learners to consider the facts and questions they have about the challenge. Reflection time for groups to brainstorm the questions they would want to answer to better understand the challenge followed by a few minutes of group sharing and feedback on areas where trainers feel they could explore further or think about something differently.

Introduce Solutions Mapping and encourage the learners to consider the solution efforts and resources they already know about, as well as the questions they have about the landscape of current solutions.

Introduce the Impact Gaps followed by a short discussion about broad types of impact gaps that the groups are willing to address.

Right after the session

Group reflection discussion, Q&A, and final examples of how others have put the Canvas to use and how it might be useful as they take their work forward.

Methods

Cooperative Learning

Group work

Debriefing

What are the key learning points about using Impact Gaps Canvas to solve a challenge or problem?

References

The Impact Gaps Canvas: <https://tacklingheropreneurship.com/the-impact-gaps-canvas/>

Workshop: Writing a 10-word Impact Statement

Purpose

Teach learners how to generate proper and clear impact statements

Time

20 Minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young people, entrepreneurs

Objectives

Demonstrate the characteristics of a good impact statement

Materials

- Pen
- Paper
- Board

Facilitation steps

The 10-word impact statement tells everyone what a social enterprise set out to accomplish. After carrying out the SOAR Analysis and filling out the Impact Gaps Canvas, it is easier to define the measurable social impact of a social enterprise because the capacity and the challenges to be addressed by the social enterprise are identified during these procedures. Here are the components of a good measurable impact statement:

- 1) A verb–action word
- 2) A target population (target groups, customers, users, and beneficiaries)
- 3) A measurable outcome

Instructions

Make groups of learners – you can keep the same groups that are created in the previous activity.

Hand out a blank paper to each group.

Ask the groups to write alternative three different 10-word impact statements based on the challenge they want to address based on the results from Impact Gaps Canvas.

Make sure that each group share the statements with the other learners. During this procedure, ask the learners to evaluate the measurability of the impact.

Examples of topics:

- Establish social finance instruments for 100 women entrepreneurs
- Develop language development materials for 50 children with autism

Methods

Cooperative Learning

Group work

Debriefing

What is an impact statement good for?

References

Writing an Impact Statement: Four Things You Need to Know

<https://www.enago.com/academy/writing-an-impact-statement-four-things-you-need-to-know/>

Resources

Further reading

The impact gaps canvas. (n.d.). Tackling heropreneurship. <https://tacklingheropreneurship.com/the-impact-gaps-canvas/>

Writing Effective Impact Statements: Who Cares? So What? (n.d.). College of Agriculture and Life Sciences Communication and Marketing.

<https://www.communications.cals.vt.edu/resources/impact-statements.html>

Video materials

What is Social Entrepreneurship? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aTo0qtdVMpM>

Impact Entrepreneurship | Why impact and why now? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J-DxIF7W1Bk>

What is Impact Assessment? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m6F-gNyjayA>

Module 4. Creating social enterprises

Introduction

In this module, youth workers will be supported to provide their learners with an idea of different social business models through real examples and help them innovate impacts using the existing ones.

- The concept of social business
- Social Business Models
- Examples of Social Business Models

Competences

The youth workers will be able to:

- Identify different social business models
- Explain the concept of social enterprise and its key elements
- Show learners how to analyse
- Guide learners on how to relate the business model and real examples
- Help them to re-construct and innovate the impacts based on real examples

The youth workers will facilitate the acquisition and improvement of the following entrepreneurial competences.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Working with others
- Learning through experience
- Being analytical
- Innovative thinking

Duration

This module includes education materials with study time of approximately 2 hours.

Inventing your own social enterprise

Social enterprises apply business models to social problems aiming to create a social impact. The ultimate goal is to achieve sustainability by enabling profit to support businesses financially instead of relying on donations and grants. Since there are no shareholders, the social enterprises operate by providing goods and services and re-invest this profit in the work of the organization.

In Europe the term 'social enterprise' is used to cover the following types of business:

- Those for who the social or societal objective is of the common good and is the reason for the commercial activity, often in the form of a high level of social innovation
- Those where profits are reinvested to achieve this social objective
- Those where the method of organisation or ownership system reflects the enterprise's mission, using democratic or participatory principles or focusing on social justice

Taking into consideration of these business types, social enterprises need to adopt an effective business model with essential two key elements:

- an operating strategy that includes internal organizational structure and external partnerships that are crucial for creating the organization’s intended impact
- a resource strategy that defines where and on what terms the organization will acquire the resources (financial and human) it needs to do its work.

The business model for a social enterprise is the channel that the social entrepreneur converts ideas into actions by generating both social value (measurable impact) and economic value (revenue). Depending on the impact model of the social enterprise, the following business models are established:

Business Models	How it works	Examples	Key success factors
Entrepreneur Support	Sells business support to its target population.	Microfinance organizations, consulting, or tech support	Appropriate training for the entrepreneur
Market Connection Model	Provide services to clients to help them access markets.	Supply cooperatives like fair trade, agriculture, and handicraft organizations	Low start-up costs, allow clients to stay and work in their community
Employment	Provide employment opportunity and job training to clients and then sells its products or services on the open market.	Disabilities or youth organizations providing work opportunities in landscape, cafes, printing, or other business	Job training appropriateness and commercial viability
Fees-for-service	social initiative charges the customer directly for socially beneficial services	Membership organizations, museums, and clinics	Establishing the appropriate fee structure vis a vis the benefits
Low-income client	Similar to fee-for-service in terms of offering services to clients but focuses on providing access to those who couldn’t otherwise afford it.	Healthcare (prescriptions, eyeglasses), utility programs	Creative distribution systems, lower production and marketing costs, high operating efficiencies

Cooperative	Provides members with benefits through collective services.	Bulk purchasing, collective bargaining (union), agricultural coops, credit unions	Members have common interests/needs, are key stakeholders, and investors
Market linkage	Facilitates trade relationships between clients and the external market.	Import-export, market research, and broker services	Does not sell clients' products but connects clients to markets
Service subsidization	Sells products or services to an external market to help fund other social programs. This model is integrated with the non-profit organization; the business activities and social programs overlap.	Consulting, counselling, employment training, leasing, printing services, and so forth	tangible assets (buildings, land, employees) or intangible (expertise, methodologies, or relationships)
Organizational support	Similar to service subsidization, but applying the external model; business activities are separate from social programs	Similar to service subsidization—implement any type of business that leverages its assets	Similar to service subsidization

Business model case studies

Tolkido

Tolkido, visual training materials, which was born in 2016 inspired by the problems in the life of a child with autism, is part of the education of thousands of children today. Tolkido sets out with the inspiration that one of the project's founders got from his cousin who has autism. Starting as a scientific research project, the prototype was tested with more than 500 children in 60 special education centres in 15 months of research. Every 6 months, the product was developed with feedback from experts.

The campaign, which started in cooperation with Turkey's leading autism associations and foundations, created a fund for families in need who want to use Tolkido in their education.

For further information about Tolkido, you can go to <https://tolkido.com/>

Self-reflection questions:

- What social business model does Tolkido adopt?
- Do you think it is a for-profit or non-profit social organization?
- What value do they provide to its target group?

Foster skills

Marquis Cabrera, the founder of Foster Skills, researched the foster care space and found staggering statistics. He said, “One of the statistics said 66 per cent of kids who age out of the foster care system will be homeless, in jail or dead by the time they turned 19, and I thought, ‘That’s crazy.’ So in 2010 when I was a junior in college, I started Foster Skills.”

Foster Skills helps kids transition out of foster care by providing support and building trust. Also, it addresses the simple fact: today's foster youth, through no fault of their own, are paying the price for either the shortcomings of individuals, systemic inaction and imprudent action and many times both.

Self-reflection questions:

- What social business model does Foster Skills adopt?
- Please go to the webpage of Foster Skills and navigate between the pages to explore the social enterprise.
- If Cabrera did not have first-hand experience, would it be really successful? How do you think it contributed to its success?

MamaPan

The MamaPan project was born after finding that a very low percentage of single mothers or large numbers of dependent children were able to find work and find work due to their special family circumstances. So MamaPan gave attention to this economically vulnerable group, which risks significant marginalization and social exclusion, and offered them a work schedule and reasonably paid jobs that would allow them to devote time to their families.

Self-reflection questions:

- What social business model does Mama Pan adopt?
- Please go to the webpage of MamaPan and navigate between the pages to explore the social enterprise.
- Now, what key strengths can you identify in Mama Pan as a social enterprise?

Orange Fiber

Each year Sicily’s orange juice industry produced 700,000 tonnes of waste and two Italian designers decided to put it to good use, by patenting and manufacturing the first sustainable fabric from citrus juice by-products. The newly created lightweight materials were already featured in Salvatore Ferragamo Summer/Spring 2017 collection and H&M’s annual Conscious Exclusive collection 2019. In 2015 the company won the Global Change Award from the H&M Foundation responding to the need for sustainability and innovation of fashion brands.

Self-reflection questions:

- What social business model does Orange Fiber adopt?

- Please go to the webpage of Orange Fiber and navigate between the pages to explore the social enterprise.
- Now, what value does Orange Fiber propose to its customers?

B.I.E.D.A.

A social enterprise established in Łódź is part of the landscape of unique cultural and artistic places. The name itself says a lot about the original style and the idea for the new activity of the foundation established by alternative artists. By creating original jewellery, everyday objects, interior accessories (lamps, candlesticks, installations), and processing materials - they give them a new life and arouse admiration and interest. B.I.E.D.A. Foundation created a place in the form of a gallery and café. There is an exhibition space for artistic handicrafts, it has given an unconventional atmosphere of a cafe, where experiences are not only satisfied with the taste.

B.I.E.D.A. Foundation created two jobs for people at risk of social exclusion due to illness, disability, difficult life situations, etc.

Self-reflection questions:

- What social business model does B.I.E.D.A adopt?
- How would you state the social impact of this enterprise?

Workshop: Explore businesses and innovate them

Purpose

Support learners who are searching for good social enterprise examples

Time

60 Minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young entrepreneurs

Objectives

Analyse social enterprise examples in all aspects

Materials

- Internet
- Pen
- Paper
- Board

Facilitation steps

Make pairs of learners in your teaching environment.

Make sure that each pair has access to an Internet connection.

Ask the pairs to search about two social enterprises in their country and/or region that have created a social impact. During their research, tell the pairs to consider the following questions:

- What social business model do they adopt?
- Whom do they address?

- What values do they propose?
- What social impact do they want to create through these businesses?

After the pairs complete the research, ask them the previously stated questions.

Now, ask them to switch the social enterprises they find with other pairs and repeat the process by asking the questions.

As a follow-up, ask the learners to guess what would be their impact statements. Have them select 2 social enterprises presented and try guessing and writing impact statements for them.

Also, what would they do differently if they were the founders?

Methods

Task-based learning

Cooperative learning

Debriefing

Can businesses be explored and innovated? How?

Resources

Further reading

Social enterprise business models. (2022). MaRS Startup Toolkit.

<https://learn.marsdd.com/article/social-enterprise-business-models/>

Force, A. G. (2019). 9 Business Model Examples For Social Enterprises. Change Creator.

<https://changecreator.com/9-business-model-examples-social-enterprises/>

Video materials

How to Start a Social Enterprise <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s9XASPiNc6s>

5 Keys to Success For Social Entrepreneurs: Lluís Pareras at TEDxBarcelonaChange

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pl8c5ooHfWs>

Social Business Model Canvas: Activities <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T80n3t6GvMM>

Module 5. Business idea

Introduction

A business idea is a thought that may be used to create money. The key responsibility of a dynamic entrepreneur is to come up with a novel and valuable idea. To be viable, business ideas must meet a variety of requirements. Many firms fail soon after they launch because the concept – the drive – isn't financially viable and can't support a profitable business.

As a consequence, the main topics presented in this module are:

- What is exactly a business idea;
- How to create a business idea;
- How to simulate a business idea.

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to:

- Explain what is a business idea;
- Give examples of strategies for creating business ideas;
- Simulate business ideas.

Duration

This section will last 4 hours including both the theoretical part and the proposed workshop. The theoretical part explains the basic concepts of a business idea: what it is, how to get it and how to simulate it. The practical part will allow learners to apply strategies in order to discover practical business ideas.

An overview of business idea

A business idea is a concise and accurate explanation of a company's essential operations. You must have a clear notion of the type of business you want to launch before you begin.

A business idea gives information about:

WHICH need will your business fulfil for the customers and what kind of customers will you attract?

WHAT good or service will your business sell?

WHO will your business sell to?

HOW is your business going to sell its goods or services?

HOW MUCH will your business depend upon and impact the environment? A good business idea will be compatible with the sustainable use of natural resources and will respect the social and natural environment on which it depends.

In the early stages of the entrepreneurial process, business idea descriptions are a valuable source of knowledge. A business idea may be characterized as a description of how a company operates and generates income. As a result, it is inextricably linked to the entrepreneur's vision and organizational purpose statements, which play a key role in organizational strategy, stakeholder perceptions and actions, and ideology. As a result, company concepts supply information that is likely to establish the groundwork for the incorporation's future growth and success.

Sometimes what you enjoy doing may not translate into a profitable business idea. The first idea may not always be the best one. It is important to get factual information about the market before acting on the idea.

Tips and tricks to create a business idea

It's better to keep your mind open to all possibilities while coming up with business ideas. The first step is to generate as many ideas as possible and create a list of all potential business prospects. You'll have more options with a list! Then you may go through the list and select the idea(s) that sound most plausible to you and that you believe will be the most profitable.

There are a variety of methods for generating company ideas, including polling area companies or questioning current business owners. We'll look at a few different techniques for coming up with company ideas in the sections below:

Learn from successful business owners

You can learn a lot from people in your area who have already gone through the process of establishing a business. You should try to get the following information from them:

- What kind of idea did these businesses start with?
- Where did the ideas come from?
- How did they develop their ideas into successful businesses?
- How do the business profit and fit into the local environment?
- Where did they get the money to start their business?

Draw from experience

Start with yourself. What has your experience been as a customer in the marketplace? Have you ever searched all day for some items that you could not find in any store in your area? Think about the goods and services you have wanted at different times and that you have had difficulty finding. The people around you are potential customers. It is important to understand their experience trying to find goods and services that are unavailable or not exactly what they need. Listen carefully to what these people say about their shopping experience. Ask your family and friends about the things they would like to find that are not locally available. Expand your social knowledge by talking to people from different age groups, social classes, etc. You can also visit community groups, colleges, etc. for a greater understanding of the market.

Survey your local business area

Look around your local community. Find out what types of businesses are already operating in your area and see if you can identify any gaps in the market. This is an activity that will be much easier to do with a business partner or friend. Visit the closest industrial area, markets and shopping centres in your area.

Scanning your environment

You can use your creativity to find more business ideas in your area. Look at the list of existing local businesses. If the list has included most of the local markets, you may be able to learn about the industries or service providers on which the local economy relies. Think about business ideas by considering all the resources and institutions in your area: natural resources, characteristics and skills of people in the local community, import substitution, waste products, publications, trade fairs and exhibitions.

Brainstorming

Brainstorming means opening up your mind and thinking about many different ideas. You start with a word or a topic and then write down everything that comes to mind relating to that subject. You continue writing for as long as possible, putting down things that you think of, even if they seem irrelevant or odd. Good ideas can come from concepts that initially seem strange.

To be successful, you need an open mind, a good method for turning ideas into goods, and a company that can do it again and over again. A defining idea is a specific business or product concept that becomes fundamental to the life of an entrepreneur and the success of a firm. It contains the product, or product line, that propels the company to success, whether this occurs early on in the company's life cycle or later on.

Business simulation to prepare a business idea

People remember 10% of what they read (words), 20% of what they hear (sounds), 30% of what they see (images, videos), 50% of what they see and hear (watch a demonstration), 70% of what they write and say (workshops, presentations, interactive lessons) and 90% of what they do (simulation, personal experience, practically works).

As it can be seen, people remember almost all (90%) of what they did, through even simulations. To minimize any discomfort caused by a failure, a business idea should be tested as much as possible before being put into effect. This is attainable in some cases thanks to the appropriate business simulation. In the business and marketing industries, business simulators are more than just pleasant games. Professionals can utilize a business simulation game to enhance their management and organizational abilities without the hazards connected with real-world market control. Using simulations in which the input parameters can relatively easily be modified, participants can be placed in situations as varied as possible in order to prepare as well for their future business.

Some examples of games for business simulation are:

Name	Download on			Free	Buy
	PC	iOS	Android		
AdVenture Capitalist	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Farming Simulator	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
LANDLORD Idle Tycoon Business	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Marketplace Simulations	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Rise of Industry	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Simcompanies	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
The Founder	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
The Two Point Hospital	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Virtonomics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Even if the applications aren't specifically intended for the type of firm a potential entrepreneur intends to start, such business simulations are an excellent trainer for future managers. What is more, there are some platforms which aim to simulate a business, such as SimTeam or EDUardo.

Workshop: I have a business idea

Purpose

This activity is intended to help trainees come up with various business ideas.

Time

60 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young entrepreneurs

Objectives

Create a list of business ideas

Name a business idea

Rate business ideas

Justify business ideas

Materials

- The images from the introduction section (printed or on-screen)
- Templates with business ideas (see practice activity section)
- Whiteboard
- Markers

Facilitation steps

1. Introduction (5 min)

Task: Present problems that some businesses or customers encounter and find solutions for them.

Emphasize that: A business idea should always have customers and their needs in mind.

2. Theoretical part (10min)

Explain: Tips and tricks (strategies) to create a business idea;

3. Practice activity (25 min)

Form groups of 3-5 people.

Task: Note your experiences as a customer or what other people have said about their experiences as customers in the space below. Then write down the related business idea that would provide customers with the goods or services they need and want.

Personal experience	Business ideas
Other people's experiences as customers	Business ideas
Comments about poor service	Business ideas
Difficulties encountered while trying to accomplish something	Business ideas
Environmental problems	Business ideas

4. Wrap up (10 min)

Each group decides which is their best business idea and gives it a name;

The trainer asks one member of each group to write the name of their best business idea on the board (to be more specific: if there are five groups, then on the boards will be written five titles of business ideas);

5. Evaluation (10 min)

The trainer reads all the titles and asks the trainees to vote for which they would invest (note that each member can vote only once);

The most voted idea is the winner;

The creators of it are asked to give details about it (explain how they came up with it).

The trainees discuss why they voted for it.

Methods

Simulations

Problem-based learning

Debriefing

Describe the process running from generating to justifying a business idea.

References

Generate your business idea – https://www.ilo.org/empent/areas/start-and-improve-your-business/WCMS_436192/lang--en/index.htm

Resources

Further reading

Ahmad, N.A.; Rasul, M.S.; Othman, N.; Jalaludin, N.A. Generating Entrepreneurial Ideas for Business Development. Sustainability 2022, 14, 4905. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14094905>

Brannback, M. & Carsrud, A. (2016). Fundamentals for becoming a successful entrepreneur: from business idea to launch and management, Paul Boger. https://books.google.ro/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Ih_qCgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT14&dq=business+idea&ots=1wDoYDM0DD&sig=Q0tRgysTh05Jy8NBavoljyqj1BM&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=business%20idea&f=false

Kim, W. C. & Mauborgne, R. (2000). Knowing a winning business idea when you see one. Harvard Business Review. http://hse-entrepreneur.narod.ru/knowning_idea.pdf

Scott, J. T., (2017). The entrepreneur's guide to building a successful business. EFMD. <https://efmdglobal.org/wp-content/uploads/The-Entrepreneurs-Guide-to-Building-a-Successful-Business-2017.pdf>

Video materials

Ask Ramit - What's the Best Way to Find a Business Idea? https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i9PBwA_QDig

Startup Valuation - A Guide to what your Startup is Worth <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZQWBHYtCuiE>

What are Business Simulations? | TOPSIM <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9QUIGhO9-28>

Module 6. SOAR analysis for creating a value proposition

Introduction

In this module, the learners will be supported to learn how to promote the creation of a value proposition using an asset-based approach in an entrepreneurship learning environment. To this aim, the following topics will be focused on:

- Description of Value Proposition
- Characteristics of a Good Value Proposition
- Description of S.O.A.R. Analysis
- Comparison of S.O.A.R. and SWOT Analysis
- Application of S.O.A.R. Analysis

Competences

The learners will be able to:

- Define what a value proposition is
- Describe S.O.A.R Analysis
- Compare S.O.A.R and SWOT Analysis
- Design an activity based on S.O.A.R Analysis to help young people to identify their strengths and opportunities
- Apply S.O.A.R Analysis in an entrepreneurship learning environment
- Promote youth's self-awareness and self-efficacy

The youth workers will facilitate the acquisition and improvement of the following entrepreneurial competences.

- Communication
- Teamwork
- Planning
- Creativity
- Self-awareness
- Self-efficacy

Duration

This module includes education materials with study time of approximately 3 hours.

Value Proposition

A value proposition is a statement that answers “why” someone should do business with you. It defines the benefits and tangible results that your target audience gets from using your products and services. An effective and well-defined value proposition can benefit a social enterprise by helping focus on operations and differentiating from the other enterprises in the marketplace. Considering social enterprises are about delivering value to a broad range of stakeholders and society, a value proposition is really a powerful tool to reflect your marketing efforts and communicate the social value that a social enterprise brings to others together with many benefits and importance for the success of social enterprises:

- Creates a strong differential between you and your competitors

- Improves customer engagement and conversion
- Potential investors can quickly understand what your enterprise has to offer
- Improve your operation efficiency

The top Characteristics of a Good Value Proposition include:

- Be concise and clear to understand
- Define your target customer – to who does your enterprise offer services/products
- Define the type of value and/or benefit derived from what a social enterprise offers
- Explain what you do to generate the benefit of a social enterprise

To generate a value proposition for a social enterprise, search for something unique and different starts with an analysis of strengths and opportunities for the start of marketing strategy planning to deliver the benefit to the stakeholders and society by making a SOAR (Strengths, Opportunities, Aspiration, Results) analysis with the involvement of all levels of an enterprise.

SOAR (Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results) Analysis

SOAR analysis is a strategic technique which helps organizations to focus on the current strengths and opportunities and to create a vision of future aspirations and desired results.

Both existing and new organizations can do a SOAR analysis. A SOAR Analysis is also useful for organisations that strive for breakthroughs, wish to improve their skills or focus on other development plans. The output from a SOAR analysis is a set of actions that enhance strengths and opportunities to strive for shared aspirations with measurable results. It provides a basis for further in-depth analysis using other business tools.

SOAR Analysis can be used to:

- Explore new initiatives
- Develop a strategic plan
- Focus and redirect resources
- Implement a leadership development program

Why should we do SOAR Analysis? SOAR Analysis is useful for the stakeholders to recognize the potential of the organization. It is also powerful to create a shared vision of the future among the team members and encourage their action.

Advantages of SOAR Analysis:

- Help organizations or individuals set goals and targets to achieve
- Forward-looking and positive
- Better than SWOT Analysis for startups because the organization is so new and the weaknesses and threats can be difficult to identify.
- Action-oriented
- Focus on Appreciative Inquiry

Disadvantages of SOAR Analysis

- Remember that although it builds on your strengths, it does not do an in-depth analysis of the marketplace or customers. This can lead to focusing on the wrong thing.

How does SOAR compare to SWOT?

SWOT	SOAR
Analysis Oriented	Action oriented
Competitive mindset (Be Better!)	Collaborative mindset (Be the best!)
Tactical action plan	Visionary based action plan
Top down	Engagement at all levels
Strategic improvement on weaknesses	Strategic improvement built on strength and vision
Energy depleting: There are too many weaknesses and threats	Energy creating: We are good and can become great!

SOAR analysis template

A SOAR analysis template is structured as a simple 2 x 2 matrix, resulting in four quadrants highlighting Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results.

<p>Strengths</p> <p><i>This concerns the foremost strengths of an organization. It refers to all capacities, skills, and accomplishments along with key assets and resources.</i></p> <p><i>Example questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> √ <i>What do we excel at?</i> √ <i>What have been the greatest achievements so far?</i> √ <i>What is the organization most proud of?</i> √ <i>What makes us unique?</i> √ <i>What strengths are most valuable in our marketplace?</i> √ <i>What do we do or have that's better than anyone else?</i> 	<p>Opportunities</p> <p><i>This concerns possibilities and chances to eventually leverage for success.</i></p> <p><i>Example questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> √ <i>What are the top 3 opportunities on which we should focus our efforts?</i> √ <i>What partnerships would lead to greater success?</i> √ <i>What changes and trends align with our strengths?</i> √ <i>What needs and wants are we not fulfilling?</i> √ <i>Which gaps are there that we could fill?</i>
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Aspirations	Results
<p><i>An expression of what you want to be and achieve in the future. A vision to build on current strengths, provide inspiration, and challenge the current situation.</i></p> <p><i>Example questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">√ <i>What do we deeply care about?</i>√ <i>What impacts do we want to achieve in the future?</i>√ <i>What should our future social business look like?</i>√ <i>How can we make a difference?</i>√ <i>What actions support our preferred future?</i>	<p><i>This shows how you will know that you achieved your aspirations indicated by tangible, and measurable results.</i></p> <p><i>Example questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">√ <i>How do we know when we've achieved our goals?</i>

How to execute SOAR Analysis

Remember that SOAR is a team activity!

To get the best possible outcomes from your SOAR Analysis, include team members with a broad range of perspectives.

The time needed to conduct an effective SOAR analysis will vary from 75 minutes to 2 hours including all stages.

Workshop: SOAR analysis exercise

Purpose

Help learners to create a strategic plan for their social business by using the SOAR Analysis

Time

75 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young entrepreneurs

Objectives

Define strategic priorities for learners' business plans

Creating an impact development plan

Materials

- Pen
- Paper
- Flipchart

- Sticky notes

Facilitation steps

Start by stating the purpose of the SOAR exercise and ensure everyone is on the same page.

Nominate someone as a facilitator. Use a flipchart and sticky notes for brainstorming.

Let the group define a strategic plan as a case and decide on action steps to develop it.

Stop after 30 minutes of brainstorming. Group similar ideas and themes.

Vote and prioritize issues

Create an action plan assigning responsibility for each issue to each group member

Methods

Case study

Cooperative Learning

Debriefing

How can SOAR be used in (social) entrepreneurship?

Resources

Further reading

Cuofano, G. (2022). What Is A SOAR Analysis And How To Use It? FourWeekMBA.

<https://fourweekmba.com/soar-analysis/>

Laidre, A. (2012). Starting a Business - Define Your Value Proposition. iPlanner.

https://www.iplanner.net/business-financial/online/how-to-articles.aspx?article_id=value-proposition

Shewan, D. (2022). 7 of the Best Value Proposition Examples We've Ever Seen. WordStream.

<https://www.wordstream.com/blog/ws/2016/04/27/value-proposition-examples>

Video materials

SOAR Analysis Explained https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d99QTRc_GKw

Value Propositions: What They Are and How to Create Them (with Examples)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ky67kLp1cOM>

Value Proposition Canvas Tesla <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zlf2iRRufGE>

Module 7. Business models

Introduction

This section introduces you to the main topics of business models. Trainers will learn what drives business model innovation and why it is valuable to any business. The trainer could apply practical tools to (re)design and test a business model. The trainer will be inspired by real-life business model examples from fellow entrepreneurs and learn from leading experts who design business model innovations. By the end of this course, the trainer is able to structure the trainees thinking and to communicate their business model ideas and learn how to improve their own business.

The main topics presented in this module are:

- What is a Business Model?
- Understanding Business Models
- Types of Business Models

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to define:

- What a business model is.
- Why business models matter to your firm and the value they bring.
- How business model innovation improves business performance.
- How tooling can help you to innovate your business model.

Duration

The module will last 4 hours including the workshop proposed. In the theory section, explanations of the basic concepts of a Business model are given. The practical part will allow learners to engage in collaborative learning activities to get more familiar with different business models.

This module is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and videos.

What is a business model

The term business model refers to a company's plan for making a profit. It identifies the products or services the business plans to sell, its identified target market, and any anticipated expenses. Business models are important for both new and established businesses.

By business model we mean a design for the successful operation of a business. It describes how you will reach customers, give them something they value, and make enough money from doing so to achieve your social impact.

They help new, developing companies attract investment, recruit talent, and motivate management and staff. Established businesses should regularly update their business models or they'll fail to anticipate trends and challenges ahead. Business models help investors evaluate companies that interest them.

A business model is a high-level plan for profitably operating a business in a specific marketplace. A primary component of the business model is the value proposition. This is a description of the goods or services that a company offers and why they are desirable to customers or clients, ideally stated in a way that differentiates the product or service from its competitors.

Successful businesses have business models that allow them to fulfil client needs at a competitive price and a sustainable cost. Over time, many businesses revise their business models from time to time to reflect changing business environments and market demands.

When evaluating a company as a possible investment, the investor should find out exactly how it makes its money. This means looking through the company's business model. Admittedly, the business model may not tell you everything about a company's prospects. But the investor who understands the business model can make better sense of the financial data.

Types of business models

There are as many types of business models as there are types of business. For instance, direct sales, franchising, advertising-based, and brick-and-mortar stores are all examples of traditional business models. There are hybrid models as well, such as businesses that combine internet retail with brick-and-mortar stores or with sporting organizations like the NBA.

Each business model is unique within these broad categories. Consider the shaving industry. Gillette is happy to sell its Mach3 razor handle at cost or for a lower price in order to get steady customers for its more profitable razor blades. The business model rests on giving away the handle to get blade sales. This type of business model is actually called the razor-razorblade model, but it can apply to companies in any business that sells a product at a deep discount in order to supply a dependent good at a considerably higher price.

Some examples of business models are:

Cash Machine - a concept based on the so-called negative cash conversion cycle. It is based on the assumption that the business raises funds from customers faster than it has to pay its suppliers, partners and employees.

Integrator - under this concept, the organization controls all parts of the value chain. This allows it not only to have maximum control over every element of the business but also to react instantly to any changes in its environment.

Freemium - a model extremely popular in the Internet era. It assumes free access to a given service with the possibility of purchasing additional functionalities.

Open Business - i.e. collaboration of various entities in order to develop the most innovative solutions. This model assumes great openness and transparency of an organization that decides to share its activities and encourage other companies, also competitive, to cooperate.

Subscription model - a one-time payment of a user for goods or services, paid on a regular basis. This model not only gives great comfort to the client (who does not have to make transactions all the time), but also to the organization that has the ability to precisely plan revenues.

User design - a model in which part of the value chain (mainly product design) is "outsourced" to the customers of the organization. Thanks to this, the company uses the creativity and talent of its recipients, and they have the opportunity to participate in the process of creating the product and gain additional gratification.

Pay What You Want - according to this model, it is the consumer who decides how much he can pay for the product. This allows the organization to establish a very close, trust-based relationship with it, as well as distinguish itself in highly competitive sectors.

Selling experiences - in a competitive market, we can no longer sell only a product or service. This model also assumes offering an additional "positive experience" for the consumer.

Razor and Blade - this model is based on the concept in which the basic product is offered at a low price, while the income for the organization is generated by the accessories necessary for its operation.

Workshop: Business models that have changed the world

This activity involves participants in discussions and application of the brainstorming method to build knowledge and make trainees aware that innovative business models are possible in any business activity.

Purpose

To increase the level of knowledge of participants related to Business Models and how to implement them in their businesses.

To visualize in real life how the business models can be applied.

Time

45 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

Objectives

Acknowledge existing types of Business Models in practice

Identify business models that are especially inspiring in building your own solutions

Materials

- What is The Cash Conversion Cycle - CCC? <https://youtu.be/p72xAATgpfM>
- What is Crowdfunding? Crowd Funding planning? What, How, Why and when <https://youtu.be/8b5-iEnW70k>
- How Zara Took Over The Industry Using Fast Fashion https://youtu.be/l8_gmYNCQ1g
- Cardboards (min. 50cm X 70cm)
- Sheets, colour pencils
- Handouts: Business models printed and handed to each group

Facilitation steps

1. Intro (5 min)

The class should be divided into groups of three people. giving each team one business model to watch

2. Group work and presentation (30min)

Each team should read the Theory, definitions and types of Business Models and discuss in the groups which model better suits their idea of business and why.

Each group must present the results of their discussion on a poster

The same group will watch one of the films proposed by the trainer and discuss why is an innovative business model and how can be adapted to their own business ideas.

The teams will have 2 minutes to present their conclusions and try to convince the others that this model is the best model and should be used by everybody.

3. “Summing up” and theoretical input (10 min)

The trainer and the participants will use this time to clarify the concepts and solve any doubts from the course participants. The trainer will present selected resources important for this topic

Methods

The activity is based on active participation and team projects.

Presentation, discussion, and workshop

Debriefing

What do most successful businesses seem to have in common?

References

A selection of articles discussing various frameworks to analyse business models and to understand business model innovation. Also diverse case studies of companies with innovative business models.

Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y. (2013). Designing business models and similar strategic objects: the contribution of IS. *Journal of AIS*, 14(5):237-244

Velt, D., Clemons, E., Benlian, A., Buxmann, P., Hess, T., Spann, M., Kundisch, D., Leimeister, J., and Loos, P. (2014). Business models - an information systems research agenda. *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, 6(1):45-53.

Workshop: How to revolutionize your own organisation

Purpose

To increase the level of knowledge of participants related to Business Models and how to implement them in their own businesses.

To visualize in real life how the business models can be applied.

Time

45 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

Objectives

Identify business models that are especially inspiring in building your own solutions

Materials

- Cardboards (min. 50cm X 70cm)
- Sheets, colour pencils
- Handouts: Business models printed and handed to each group

Facilitation steps

1. Intro (5min)

The class should be divided into groups of three people. giving to each team the possibility to work on a specific business project. The group will decide which product or service they will offer.

2. Group work and presentation (30min)

The groups should answer the following questions that will give them the opportunity to build their organization's business model.

Who? - who is our client? What are his needs and desires?

What? - what can we offer to the client? How can we respond to his desires? What will be our value proposition?

How? - how will we deliver value to the customer? What processes inside the organization will we need?

Why? - how are we going to cash our efforts? How will customers pay for our services and stuff our pockets?

Each group must present the results of their discussion on a poster

3. “Summing up” and theoretical input (10 min)

The trainer and the participants will use this time to clarify the concepts and solve any doubts from the course participants.

To the very concept of a business model, we must add the methodology of its materialization, implementation and integration with other modes of organization.

Methods

The course will be based on active participation, workshop exercise, and team projects.

Presentation, discussion, and workshop

Debriefing

What are the key questions to ask yourself in order to revolutionize your organisation?

References

There are numerous articles discussing various frameworks to analyse business models and to understand business model innovation; also, diverse case studies of companies with innovative business models.

Alex Osterwalder, “Tools for Business Model Generation,” Stanford eCorner, February 2012, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8GlbCg8NpBw>.

Business Model Fiddle, <https://bmfiddle.com/>.

Canvanizer, <https://canvanizer.com/new/business-model-canvas>

Example from Business Model Generation, BMFiddle, <https://bmfiddle.com/f/#/local>.

Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y. (2013). Designing business models and similar strategic objects: the contribution of IS. *Journal of AIS*, 14(5):237-244

Velt, D., Clemons, E., Benlian, A., Buxmann, P., Hess, T., Spann, M., Kundisch, D., Leimeister, J., and Loos, P. (2014). Business models - an information systems research agenda. *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, 6(1):45-53.

Resources

Further reading

Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers. John Wiley & Sons. (2)R2. Amit, R., & Zott, C. (2001).

Video materials

What is The Cash Conversion Cycle - CCC? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p72xAAAgpfM>

What is Crowdfunding? CrowdFunding planning? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8b5-iEnW70k>

How Zara Took Over The Industry Using Fast Fashion

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l8_gmYNCQ1g

Freemium: The First Business Model of the 21st Century

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZOKcedfE_nM

Scott Stratten | Authentic & Transparent Marketing

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gIX6QNsQ9kg>

Module 8. Social business models

Introduction

As indicated previously, the phrase "business model" refers to a company's profit strategy. It specifies the items or services that the company intends to sell, as well as its target market and any estimated costs. Therefore, a business model canvas is a visual depiction of a company model that highlights all of the important strategic elements. In other words, it's a broad, comprehensive, and all-encompassing perspective of the company's operations, customers, income sources, and more.

Whereas, the Social Business Model Canvas is based on the Business Model Canvas, but applied especially for social enterprise. The purpose is to assist social innovators by assisting them in the development of their business models. Rather than focusing on earnings, social businesses focus on the impact they have on beneficiaries.

This section provides learners with a good understanding of social entrepreneurship, and the fundamentals for creating you're their own social enterprise plan. This section provides an excellent introduction to Social Entrepreneurship getting started and how individuals have a role in creating social change. The trainer could apply practical tools to (re)design and test a social enterprise plan. The trainer will be inspired by real-life business model examples from fellow entrepreneurs and learn from leading experts who design social enterprise plans. By the end of this course, the trainer is able to structure the trainees thinking and communicate their business model ideas and learn how to improve their own business models.

Therefore, the main topics presented in this module are:

- Literature review of social enterprise
- Simple and fast track method
- An overview of the social business model canvas
- Long Path - Social Business Model
- Example of Social Business Model Canvas

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to:

- State the characteristics of a social enterprise;
- Examine the needs of society;
- Develop a business model using the social business model canvas;
- Exemplify at least one social business model canvas.

Duration

This section will last 4 hours including both the theoretical part and the proposed workshop. The theoretical part explains the basic concepts of a social business model canvas. The practical part will allow learners to apply the knowledge by engaging in collaborative learning activities to get more familiar with Canvas business models.

This module is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and videos.

Social enterprises

A social enterprise is a business that blends revenue development and profit with the obligation to respect and assist its environment and stakeholder network. This entails paying attention to, investing in, and actively managing the trends driving today's environment. It is an organization that accepts responsibility for being a decent citizen (both inside and outside the business), serving as a role model for its peers, and encouraging high levels of cooperation at all levels of the organization.

Listening closely to the external as well as the internal environment—not just business partners and customers, but all parties in society that an organization impacts and are impacted by—is fundamental to operating as a social company. If enterprises fully make use of the people's data at their disposal, the listening opportunity is larger than ever in today's society.

Essentially, social entrepreneurship strives to provide value to society or have a beneficial influence on it by providing services or goods that answer unmet needs or by giving various solutions to social concerns. Social entrepreneurship is frequently viewed as a vehicle for resolving inequitable conditions that contribute to exclusion, marginalization, or suffering among parts of society that lack the ability to change these situations on their own. The majority of social entrepreneurs' "clients" are marginalized or disadvantaged organizations or people with little financial resources.

Formulating a specific business model for a social enterprise will help the new one, the entrepreneur, to focus on the key aspects and main goals of his potential business, but it will also be a difficult and unproductive task in the sense that it can be lost in the definition and development of the beginning of the business by keeping such a document.

Nevertheless, let's break it down into two main approaches, namely:

- Fast track path - 3 simple questions to guide you quickly and easily
- Long Path – the Social Business Model

Simple and fast track

3 questions model:

- Question 1 - What will you sell?
- Question 2 - Who will you sell to?
- Question 3 - How much will you sell for?

Exercise

Work in pairs or individually and answer those questions very carefully.

Long path

This goal will be maintained through the creation of an efficient operating system that will be able to facilitate all kinds of transactions between all relevant stakeholders and parties such as the community, customers, employers, employees, volunteers, management, sponsors and even investors. Consequently, a worthwhile social business model expresses those concrete actions that ultimately determine the key factors that are capable of leading to the sustainable development of social enterprise, including ways to detect potential threats, ways to build consortia and form strong alliances, ways to attract investors, ways to estimating potential outcomes - including socially and environmentally oriented outcomes - and even ways to prove that the social enterprise and its

management team are actually operating within the context of a complete business plan, which demonstrates some professionalism.

Today, there are many business planning templates that are easy to find on the web. They have been thoroughly modified in a way that serves not only the usual types of enterprises but also specific forms such as social enterprises, for example. Consequently, it would be more desirable if potential social entrepreneurs combine elements derived from different templates to create a unique social business model that could ultimately be correlated with the final form of each social business.

After a careful study of the existing templates, it can be concluded that all social business models share the following steps - pillars:

- Determining the main purpose of the social enterprise;
- Designing a specific action plan in which all secondary goals will eventually be achieved;
- Defining specific qualitative and quantitative criteria to relate to the design, measurement and improvement of the outcomes of potential social business;
- Making decisions related to the detection of necessary resources, as well as the costs and revenues of the enterprise

Social Business Model Canvas

One of the most popular social business models is the widely known " Social Business Model Canvas". This tool helps you to plan, communicate and refine your business model in a simple, visual way.

A Business Model Canvas is a graphical depiction of a company's business model. It defines how the organization develops, delivers, and collects value, as you might expect. The Canvas, which is based on a visual language, allows everyone to comprehend the pillars and critical components of a certain business model. A fantastic tool for quickly and effectively explaining new or current business models, researching rivals' models, and presenting business ideas to external stakeholders.

MISSION				
IMPLEMENTATION		VALUE	MARKET	
Key allies	Key Resources	Social Innovation	Customer Relationships	Channels
	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer benefits	
FINANCES				
Cost of Delivery		Community Reinvestment	Revenue Streams	

Source: Social Enterprise Institute

Non-profit organizations, charities, public sector enterprises, and for-profit social businesses can all benefit from the Business Model Canvas. The sole distinction between standard business enterprise and social entrepreneurship is the organization's goal. A business enterprise is primarily concerned

with financial returns or shareholder value, whereas social entrepreneurship is more concerned with ecological, and social concerns, and public service obligations.

Social Business Model Canvas, developed by Social Innovation Lab, expands on the previous model and is often used by social companies since it considers all of the components required to achieve both social and economic sustainability.

Firstly, choose a mission. All social-purpose businesses are on a mission to change society for the better. What change are you planning to make in the world? Describe in broad terms how you will pursue your cause and tackle the social or environmental problems that matter.

1. *Customer relationships*

The network of suppliers and partners that make the business model work.

Good firms deliberate on which consumer categories to pursue and which to ignore. Who are we providing value for? Who are our most valuable clients? Concentrate on your ideal customer(s) and precisely describe them.

2. *Social innovation*

You are proposing a significant solution to a social or environmental issue. What makes your recommended remedy more likely to be effective than previous ones? Consider how you will fix the problem using new approaches, ideas, or products.

3. *Value proposition*

Your social company must stand out from the crowd and provide actual value to clients in order to be successful. What problems do you solve for your customers? What mix of advantages would you provide? Consider what you may say to persuade your consumers to buy from you.

4. *Channels*

You can employ a variety of communication, distribution, and sales methods. How will you get out to your target customers? Which will be the most effective? Prioritize the routes that are most likely to succeed.

5. *Customers benefits*

You have several communication, distribution, and sales channels to choose from. How will you reach out to your target audience? Which will be the most efficient? Concentrate first on the channels that are most likely to succeed.

6. *Key activities*

To provide value to clients and create an impact, your social company must do, deliver, or manufacture certain things. What are the mission-critical tasks you must complete?

7. *Key resources*

All businesses rely on resources to do their tasks. These might be personal, financial, physical, or technical in nature. What resources do you now have or will need to acquire or develop? Which resources will be most critical to success?

8. *Key allies*

Going it alone is unlikely to result in the success of your social venture. Who are the individuals and groups you must include in order to succeed? What added value will they provide? Consider the

funders, partners, suppliers, and others who will have an impact on your success and how you will collaborate with them.

9. *Cost of delivery*

Everything costs money, and often far more than you realize. What are the primary cost components of executing your business and satisfying needs? What are the most costly resources and activities? How will you keep your key expenses under control?

10. *Revenue streams*

To be financially viable, most social businesses rely on a variety of revenue streams. What are your primary sources of earned revenue, grants, and gifts to support our work? In an ideal world, how much would each source contribute to our total income? Consider how you will attain a long-term equilibrium.

11. *Community reinvestment*

To stay viable and fulfil their objective, all social businesses must generate a surplus (profit). How much surplus do you expect to create each year, and how much of it will be reinvested? How will you reinvest this excess to strengthen your organization and serve your community?

How to apply social business model canvas

There are different ways to start the process. Start with:

- 1) An idea – start with defining the value proposition for a specific customer segment.
- 2) Potential/existing customers – start with the customer segment and ask what value proposition you are delivering / could deliver to them and how.
- 3) Your resources – Start to think about what key resources (competences, experiences, physical resources, financial resources, etc.) you or your partners have and based on this develop your offer for a specific customer group.

Don't be tempted to start filling in the canvas from left to right. Start with the Market and Value elements of the canvas (the most important elements), and don't be tempted to start filling in the canvas from left to right. Challenge your assumptions as you go along. How do you know that what you have written in each part of the canvas is true? What evidence would you need to test your assumptions? When completed, take stock and consider the whole picture. Explore the connections and trade-offs between each section. Is the overall picture plausible? Are there things that you need to revisit or think differently about?

What is more, sticky notes are useful since they can be readily erased or modified. Distinct colours should be used for different value propositions and client segments. Also, create many versions and analyze them using a Strategic Fit and/or a SWOT analysis.

One extra aspect to reflect on: Do you know enough about your beneficiaries' or customers' needs? The first stage is to develop empathy for them and to comprehend their condition, everyday lives, desires, sorrows, and gains.

When completed, take stock and consider the whole picture.

Example of social business model canvas

MISSION: With every product you purchase, TOMS will help a person in need. One for One®.				
IMPLEMENTATION		VALUE	MARKET	
Key Allies	Key Resources	Social Innovation	Customer Relationships	Channels
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suppliers provide environmentally sound materials Shoe retailers sell product to customers Humanitarian organizations collaborate on social programs In-country volunteers distribute shoes for free in target countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working capital Large workforce Manufacturing facilities Volunteer base 	One-for-one concept is distinctive from traditional charitable giving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brand conscious millennials and hipsters People experiencing first-world consumer guilt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media Global awareness raising events Campus and schools programs Corporate cause marketing partnerships E-commerce and online advertising International network of shoe retailers
	Key Activities	Value Proposition	Consumer Benefits	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product development Manufacturing process Online selling Tracking and shipping Customer service Social programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meaningful cause High quality product Ethical company Status symbol Fresh way to donate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children educated Better family health Economic opportunity 	
FINANCES				
Cost of Delivery		Community Reinvestment	Revenue Streams	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shoe design and manufacturing Marketing Logistics Distribution of donated shoes 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One-for-one product donation Company giving program 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenue from shoe sales Sales of accessories 	

Source: Social Enterprise Institute

Workshop: Our social business model canvas

Purpose

This activity trains the participants to fill in the social business model canvas based on an existing social problem.

Time

90 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young entrepreneurs

Objectives

Give an example of at least one social problem

Complete the social business model canvas

Rate the information from their own social business model canvas

Materials

- Devices with an Internet connection
- Cardboards (min. 50cm X 70cm)
- Sheets
- Colour pencils
- Handouts: Business models printed and handed to each group

MISSION:				
IMPLEMENTATION		VALUE	MARKET	
Key Allies	Key Resources	Social Innovation	Customer Relationships	Channels
	Key Activities	Value Proposition	Consumer Benefits	
FINANCES				
Cost of Delivery		Community Reinvestment	Revenue Streams	

Facilitation steps

1. Introduction (5 min)

Task: Brainstorm our common mission.

The trainees should:

- Choose a niche
- Give examples of problems of that specific niche that encounter social values.
- Clarify their mission

Example:

Niche: students

Problem: schools can't provide school materials

Our mission: Supply the school materials for students

Tips and tricks: write down all the ideas on the board (e.g. a mind map). In the end, focus on only one niche and problem in order to find a common mission.

2. Theoretical part (10 min)

Explain

The components of the social business model canvas

3. Practical activity (50 min)

Form groups of 8-10 people

Task: Complete the online social business model canvas having in mind the chosen mission.

All the members from one group will complete the same social business model canvas

Tips and tricks:

Ask the trainees to write as many ideas as they want.

Explain the online social business model canvas:

- Name: *Mural* (<https://app.mural.co/template/348236df-bed7-4445-82c8-5c7b4f2c7c57/a6b82309-9034-4fbb-aec3-7cc1f2714419>)
- Note that it can be used both on phones or laptops. Also, it can be downloaded on Google Play and App Store (participants can use whatever they find easier)
- Help the trainees create a free account
 - Sign up button – Complete first name, last name and email – a code is sent to the email
- Show them how to share the social business model canvas with the other participant of the group.
 - Share button – Choose the link or email
- Participants are asked to write all their ideas
 - Double Click and a sticky note appear

4. Wrap up (5 min)

Task: Take a look at all your written ideas and vote for the best ones. The most voted represent are part of your social business model canvas.

Tips and tricks:

Each group do this task based on their own social business model canvas

Explain how to vote:

- On the left corner of the page, there is a “Voting session” button
- Click “Start voting session”
- Complete: votes per person – 1, what to vote on – ONLY sticky notes
- Start the voting session

End the voting session after 5 minutes

5. Evaluation (15 min)

Each group do this task based on their own social business model canvas.

Each group receive a SWOT analyze template.

SWOT Analysis	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
Your advantages	Areas for improvement
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
Situations to apply your advantages	Where you are at risk

Regarding their final product of the social business model canvas, a team member takes the SWOT template and writes down maximum three ideas, then passes it to the next person who adds new ideas or comments on the first set of ideas (max. 3). The paper is passed around until everyone gets a chance to add their thoughts.

In the end, the SWOT analysis is discussed.

Methods

Brainstorming

Problem-solving

Voting

Debriefing

SWOT analysis, brainwriting

References

Śliwowski, K. (2021, January 24). Open business model canvas, or how to describe an idea for open business? Sektor 3.0. Retrieved October 16, 2021, from <https://sektor3-0.pl/en/blog/open-business-model-canvas-or-how-to-describe-an-idea-for-open-business/>

Social Business Model Canvas - Social Enterprise Institute. (n.d.). Retrieved October 16, 2021, from <https://socialenterpriseinstitute.co/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Social-Business-Model-Canvas.pdf>

A new social business model Canvas online. (n.d.). Retrieved October 16, 2021, from <https://socialbusinessmodelcanvas.swarthmore.edu/>

Resources

Further reading

Anika, H. (2018). How to Master the Business Model Canvas for Social Entrepreneurs. Tbd.
<https://www.tbd.community/en/a/how-master-business-model-canvas-social-entrepreneurs>

Social Business Model Canvas. A new Social Business Model Canvas online.
<https://socialbusinessmodelcanvas.swarthmore.edu>

Using the business model canvas for social enterprise design. <https://cscuk.fcdo.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/BMC-for-Social-Enterprise.pdf>

Video materials

The Nonprofit Business Model Canvas: <https://youtu.be/4pcnRIPJvj8>

Social enterprise and Social business model: <https://youtu.be/Zwvk5f8Hllk>

Overview of the Social Business Model Canvas: <https://youtu.be/8aPGXqLZCS0>

Business Model Canvas Explained: <https://youtu.be/QoAOzMTLP5s>

Strategy Made Simple (2020). Video: Overview of the Social Business Model Canvas.
<https://strategymadesimple.ca/blog/video-overview-of-the-social-business-model-canvas>

Module 9. Pitch your business

Introduction

In this module, you will learn how to use your own expertise, you will refine your list of business opportunities in stages to your three most viable ideas. Then you will enter these ideas into a peer-to-peer collaboration platform to receive feedback from the wisdom of the crowd. Finally, you will develop a one-minute pitch, practice it with a partner, and record it. You and your classmates will view and provide feedback on each other's pitches. By the end of this course, you will have selected your best product or service idea and prepared a polished pitch to present to stakeholders.

Competences

By the end of this course, you will have selected your best product or service idea and prepared a polished pitch to present to stakeholders.

- Use your own expertise to select a subset of your best product and service ideas
- Rate product and service ideas through a peer-to-peer digital platform
- Prepare and receive feedback on a one-minute pitch video for your best idea

Duration

The module will last 4 hours including the workshop. In the educational section, there is an explanation of the basic concepts of the Pitch your idea model and how to implement it. Some important aspect to take into account is the division – parts of the pitch and reading with attention the examples proposed by the trainer. The exercise suggested in the activity section of the module will allow participants to practice the concepts acquired in the module first-hand.

Definition

An elevator pitch, elevator speech, or elevator statement is a short description of an idea, product, or company that explains the concept in a way such that any listener can understand it in a short period of time. This description typically explains who the thing is for, what it does, why it is needed, and how it will get done. Finally, when explaining to an individual, the description generally explains one's skills and goals, and why they would be a productive and beneficial person to have on a team or within a company or project. An elevator pitch does not have to include all of these components, but it usually does at least explain what the idea, product, company, or person is and their value.

An elevator pitch can be used to entice an investor or executive in a company or explain an idea to a founder's parents. The goal is simply to convey the overall concept or topic in an exciting way. Unlike a sales pitch, there may not be a clear buyer–seller relationship.

There are many origin stories for the elevator pitch. One commonly-known origin story is that of Ilene Rosenzweig and Michael Caruso, two former journalists active in the 1990s. According to Rosenzweig, Caruso was a senior editor at *Vanity Fair* and was continuously attempting to pitch story ideas to the Editor-In-Chief at the time, but could never pin her down long enough to do so simply because she was always on the move. So, in order to pitch her ideas, Caruso would join her during short free periods of time she had, such as on an elevator ride. Thus, the concept of an elevator pitch was created, as says Rosenzweig.

How to implement

The advantages of conducting an elevator pitch include convenience and simplicity. For instance, elevator pitches can be given on short notice and without much preparation due to the pre-planning of the content being delivered within the said pitch, making the listener more comfortable. Furthermore, elevator pitches allow the individual who is giving the pitch the ability to simplify the content and deliver it in a less complicated manner by providing the information in a cut-down fashion that gets right to the point

Elevator pitch is a slang term used to describe a brief speech that outlines an idea for a product, service or project. The name comes from the notion that the speech should be delivered in the short time period of an elevator ride, usually 20-60 seconds.

An elevator pitch is important because it communicates the most important aspects of your business and services within that short amount of time. First, you have to decide what exactly you want to communicate about yourself or your business.

A good pitch is a balancing act that can be adjusted to the currents in the room. A recent survey of HBR readers found — at least in this community — how important it is to understand not just what you are pitching, but who you are pitching to.

Part of your pitch

Always remember: You are the most important part of the presentation. Make sure that you present yourself as a smart and grounded individual. Key factors to keep in mind are posture, purposeful hand gestures, appropriate pauses, the energy and tone of your voice, and strong eye contact.

To craft a pitch that is succinct and compelling keep these seven fundamental factors in mind.

- Be brief
- Be clear
- Make it specific to your audience
- Highlight your benefits
- Identify the problem and your solution
- Make a compelling call-to-action
- Extend an invitation to continue the conversation.

Elevator pitch examples

Brooklyn Doula: Postpartum doula; Brooklyn, New York

The Pitch: "I offer non-judgemental support throughout pregnancy, birth, and the postpartum period. Labour doula services, prenatal consults, private childbirth education, postpartum doula services, lactation support, and more are all available and tailored to your preferences."

Why it works: In her pitch, Megan Davidson, PhD aims to educate prospective clients about both her business and her profession. Many new parents don't know what a doula is—and even those who are familiar with birth doulas don't always realize that doulas can help after the baby's arrival.

"I am one of the most experienced doulas in the country, having supported over 600 families in birth and over 1350 families postpartum. I am also the author of *Your Birth Plan: A Guide to Navigating All of Your Choices in Childbirth*. I would love to speak with you more about your plans and my services," Davidson states on her website.

KangoGift: Human resources software company; Arlington, Massachusetts

The Pitch: We make it easy to say 'thank you' at work."

Why it works: KangoGift founder Todd Horton thinks too many elevator pitches describe what the company does, following a formula like, "We operate in the \$X market of Y and offer Z." Yet his company's original elevator pitch wasn't straightforward enough. He used to say, "We help companies put a gift in the hands of great employees"—referring to the idea of sending electronic gift cards to an employee's phone. Now, Horton focuses on what the KangoGift software allows users to do: say thanks. With that simple promise in mind, prospective customers then hear more about KangoGift's tools, which allow managers to celebrate work more easily and employees to receive praise more frequently. One sales pitch example he cites: A manager can send a Starbucks gift card via email or text to thank an employee who stayed late finishing a big project.

Merchant Machine: Payment processing comparison site; London, England

The Pitch: "Merchant Machine helps small businesses quickly and easily save money on their credit card processing costs by comparing the leading options in the market. It's completely free to the end user, there are no obligations and takes just one minute to do."

Why it works: Merchant Machine founder Ian Wright used to elaborate on his company's services and onboarding processes, only to realize he was leaving most people confused. So, he streamlined his pitch to focus only on the main benefit—saving money—and on overcoming common objections about cost, obligations, and time. Since then, Wright has seen people instantly understand the value of the company. Once, when he was chatting with someone at a bar, his new acquaintance pulled out his phone and got a quote from Merchant Machine for a 25% reduction in payment processing costs.

Hux: House cleaning platform; Atlanta, Georgia

The Pitch: Hux is an online platform directly connecting local consumers with house cleaners. With Hux, you can easily compare local house cleaners on total price, reviews, availability and instantly book a service. Our technology empowers local house cleaners by replacing costly overhead found in the traditional service industry and makes it easy for consumers to book services online in just two minutes. Just think of us as the Uber of house cleaning!"

Why it works: Plenty of businesses want to be the Uber of their industry—so much so that the comparison can be a cop-out for an original pitch. Hux manager Shayla Hill explains the platform on its own merits first, describing its benefits for both the consumers and housecleaners who use the service. But adding the Uber line—as she and colleagues did after clients kept making the comparison—helps drive home the platform's ease of use and instant booking features.

Cigarette Pollution Solutions: Cigarette receptacles; Los Angeles, California

The Pitch: "I make energy from cigarette butts."

Why it works: Cigarette Pollution Solutions makes the Butts Only Box, a cigarette receptacle placed in public areas like parks and beaches. But trash doesn't necessarily make for good networking conversation, so founder Ken Beckstead focuses on the treasure. His one-sentence opener begs more questions about what happens after he takes cigarette butts to a waste and energy plant to be converted into electricity.

Chellie Campbell: Financial coach, Los Angeles, California

The Pitch: Campbell's opening line is sung to the tune of "Tomorrow" from Annie: "You're gonna be rich tomorrow...if you take my class today!" She goes on to say, "I'm Chellie Campbell and I treat money disorders: spending bulimia and income anorexia. My 8-week Financial Stress Reduction Workshop is

designed to help you make more money and have more time off for fun. I'm also the author of three bestselling books, "The Wealthy Spirit," "Zero to Zillionaire" and "From Worry to Wealthy." So, if you're living on peanut butter and jelly and would like to afford deli, call Chellie!"

Why it works: When a former musical comedy actress gets into financial services, you get songs, rhyme—and, if you're Campbell, new leads. Campbell's pitch conveys that taking her financial workshop might actually be fun. She always gets laughs and often gets prospective customers, who come talk with her after seeing her pitch. Campbell has been teaching her Financial Stress Reduction Workshop since 1990, thanks in part to her creative approach to a dry topic. "I built my whole business from just giving my 30-second pitch at networking events," Campbell said.

The Pendergraft Firm: Law office; Greenbelt, Maryland

The Pitch: I'm Brian Pendergraft, Esq., and I am a full-service real estate and title attorney. I help with ABCDEF: agreements, business entity formation, closings and titles, deeds, evictions, and foreclosure. For all of your real estate legal needs, it's as simple as ABC; work with me."

Why it works: Upon hearing Pendergraft's pitch, new contacts probably won't remember what ABCDEF stands for. But they will remember Pendergraft for his attempt to be clever—and that's his main goal, anyway. "I feel like no one really cares about what you do, so they will quickly forget who you are unless you come up with something memorable," Pendergraft said, who has stuck with the pitch ever since landing a new client on his first attempt.

The Style Foundry: Style consultant; Chagrin Falls, Ohio

The Pitch: "I'm Megan Moran, and I am the owner and wardrobe stylist at The Style Foundry. We are a full-service wardrobe styling business that helps you take the stress out of getting dressed through our styling services. A typical customer cycle starts with a Closet Cleanse, where I clean out your closet, tell you what to keep and get rid of, take pictures of all of the yeses and then upload them to an app/website where I mix and match them into over 100 different outfits from what you already own. From there, I am able to really see what's missing and what you need. We can tackle that by personal shopping, which is done in-person at your favourite stores or ones I suggest; virtual shopping, which is done online (I send you my finds, you buy what you like, and then when all of the items arrive at your house, I come in for a fitting); or through our mobile boutique, which we can pull up in your driveway and fill it with our pieces that best fit your style and shopping list. It's the best of online and boutique shopping."

Why it works: In pitching her business, Moran faces a couple of challenges: People don't realize that styling services like hers are available—and they assume that they don't have the wardrobe or budget to make it work. That's why Moran added the detail about creating 100 outfits from an existing wardrobe. Explaining the process behind her services adds further validity for sceptical clients. "They realize I'm not trying to make them buy a whole new wardrobe, just weeding out a few things," she said.

Workshop: Pitch your start-up

Thanks to this activity, participants will be able to understand how to prepare a strategic pitch to succeed not only in terms of raising money but also in maximizing the mission of a firm.

Purpose

To provide a deeper understanding of the Pitch method in start-ups and new businesses. Pitching a good idea or project is the step or gap between idea generation and taking action.

Time

1.5 hours

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

Objectives

Motivate participants to transform their nice plan relating to the business start-up, development, project, etc. into a good pitch

Improve the capacity of the pitcher's ability to come up with practicable concepts that quickly and for good overshadow the catcher's feelings concerning an idea's value.

Materials

- Handout for participants: Definitions
- Classroom/training room
- Laptop with internet connection
- Sheets blogs, pencils, markers, crayons, coloured pencils
- StartupMadlibs worksheet from: https://fi.co/system/upload/StartupMadlibs_worksheet.pdf

STARTUP MADLIBS

My company, _____ ,
NAME OF COMPANY

is developing _____
A DEFINED OFFERING

to help _____
A DEFINED AUDIENCE

_____ with
SOLVE A PROBLEM

_____ .
SECRET SAUCE

Example: My company, the Founder Institute, is developing a training and mentoring program to help entrepreneurs launching a new startup create meaningful and enduring technology companies with shared equity that encourages peer support.

 Complete your Founder Institute Application Now: <http://fi.co/join>

Facilitation steps

1. Intro (15 min)

Divide the group into small teams of three people, giving to each team the possibility to discuss and build a pitch for their entrepreneurship. This step is very important because they must first agree on a business type and after to build their pitch.

2. Group work and presentation (45 min)

Each team has to read the definition and examples given in this module and find a creative way to prepare their presentation.

Some important information to print and give to the learners:

As a start-up founder, you will meet hundreds of people at various meetings, events and conferences. You will also, routinely, introduce yourself to complete strangers by email. In such situations, you have seconds to spark someone's curiosity. And the best way to do that is a compelling Elevator Pitch.

Use the template below to craft your own:

This one-sentence statement explains what you do, who you serve and why it matters in simple language. As the name implies, the summary can quickly be recited to a stranger on an elevator ride.

Let's go through each of the items

- The **defined offering** must be short, simple and capable of being understood by everyone, like "a website", "a mobile application", "hardware" or "desktop software."
- The **defined audience** is the initial group of people that you will market your offering to. In the case of consumer applications, it is usually a demographic, such as "women aged 25 to 35 years old." In the case of business applications, it is usually a job function at a type of corporation, such as "system administrators at medium-sized technology businesses."
- Now that you have an offering helping an audience, you need to **solve a problem**. The problem needs to be something that everyone understands, such as "reduce the time collecting bill payments" or "engage in an immersive entertainment experience."
- The final component, the **secret sauce**, adds your unique approach to solving the problem and demonstrates a mastery of the market. Some examples are "by sending automated email alerts based on analysis of highest response times" or "with virtual worlds constructed in reaction to the movements of the players."

Material available online at: https://fi.co/pitch_deck#elevator

The small groups will present their "Pitch elevator" to the other peers/learners that will act as investors.

3. "Summing up" and theoretical input (30 min)

The trainer and the participants will use this time to clarify the concept and ask questions. The trainer will make a summary of the good and weak points of the presentations without focusing on a special group no to des-motivate the learners.

Methods

A good pitch can be decisive for your business. Treat it as the key to opening doors to new opportunities and spending some time on it.

Group activity, Reflection, brainstorm

Debriefing

What are the dos and don'ts of a good pitch?

References

How to create the Perfect Elevator Pitch. Indeed Career Guide. (n.d.). Retrieved October 15, 2021, from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/perfect-elevator-pitch>

Resources

Further reading

Guy Kawasaki, "The 10/20/30 Rule of PowerPoint," GuyKawasaki.com, https://guykawasaki.com/the_102030_rule/.

Hernan Jaramillo, "11 Hacks to Get Meetings With Investors in Silicon Valley," HackerMoon, January 12, 2015, <https://hackernoon.com/11-hacks-to-get-meetings-with-investors-in-silicon-valley-14b4851ab3e8>.

The Myth of the Elevator Pitch. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254004669_The_Myth_of_the_Elevator_Pitch [accessed Oct 15 2021].

Video materials

How to Create the Perfect Elevator Pitch - Plus Examples: <https://youtu.be/Qncmc-yx3gl>

How to Perfect the Elevator Pitch: https://youtu.be/y1Y02_oZP8U

Elevator Pitch Example - How To Create A Personal Elevator Pitch: <https://youtu.be/wVYyCUwDFhE>

Strategyzer, "Business Model Canvas Explained," YouTube, September 1, 2011, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QoAOzMTLP5s>

Module 10. Funding opportunities

Introduction

In this module, learners will be supported in gaining knowledge of different types of financing and some opportunities available at the European level

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to:

- Selecting different types of funding
- Detecting opportunities in the European framework
- Estimating the necessary step to get funding

Duration

The module will last 2 hours including the workshop. In the theory section, there is an explanation of the basic concepts of Funding and the different types of funding available to launch a social enterprise. The exercise suggested in the activity section of the module will allow participants to practice the concepts acquired in the module firsthand.

This module is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises.

The landscape of funding

Individuals are hoping to gain funding for their companies. As the business becomes increasingly mature, it tends to advance through the funding rounds.

On the other side are potential investors. While investors wish for businesses to succeed because they support entrepreneurship and believe in the aims and causes of those businesses, they also hope to gain something back from their investment.

It is common for a company to begin with a seed round and continue with A, B and then C funding rounds. The different rounds of funding operate in essentially the same basic manner; investors offer cash in return for an equity stake in the business. Between the rounds, investors make slightly different demands on the startup.

Private funding

Pre-Seed Funding

The earliest stage of funding a new company comes so early in the process that it is not generally included in the rounds of funding at all. Known as "pre-seed" funding, this stage typically refers to the period in which a company's founders are first getting their operations off the ground. The most common "pre-seed" funders are the founders themselves, as well as close friends, supporters and family. Depending upon the nature of the company and the initial costs set up with developing the business idea, this funding stage can happen very quickly or may take a long time. It's also likely that investors at this stage are not investing in exchange for equity in the company. In most cases, the investors in a pre-seed funding situation are the company founders themselves.

Seed Funding

Seed funding is the first official equity funding stage. It typically represents the first official money that a business venture or enterprise raises. Some companies never extend beyond seed funding into Series A rounds or beyond.

There are many potential investors in a seed funding situation: founders, friends, family, incubators, venture capital companies and more. One of the most common types of investors participating in seed funding is a so-called "angel investor." Angel investors tend to appreciate riskier ventures (such as startups with little by way of a proven track record so far) and expect an equity stake in the company in exchange for their investment.

Series A Funding

Once a business has developed a track record (an established user base, consistent revenue figures, or some other key performance indicator), that company may opt for Series A funding in order to further optimize its user base and product offerings.

Series B Funding

Series B rounds are all about taking businesses to the next level, past the development stage. Investors help startups get there by expanding market reach. Companies that have gone through seed and Series A funding rounds have already developed substantial user bases and have proven to investors that they are prepared for success on a larger scale. Series B funding is used to grow the company so that it can meet these levels of demand.

European funds

The European Commission is determined to support social economy ecosystems.

EU Funding is available for all types of companies of any size and sector including entrepreneurs, start-ups, micro companies, small and medium-sized enterprises, and larger businesses. A wide range of financing is available: business loans, microfinance, guarantees and venture capital. Every year the EU supports more than 200 000 businesses.

The **decision** to provide EU financing will be **made by the local financial institutions** such as banks, venture capitalists or angel investors. Thanks to the EU's support, local financial institutions can provide additional financing to businesses.

How it works

Source: [European Commission](#)

Examples of European programs to obtain funding for a social venture:

THE START-UP AND SCALE INITIATIVE aims to give Europe's many innovative entrepreneurs every opportunity to become world-leading companies

THE SOCIAL BUSINESS INITIATIVE (SBI), analyses business cooperation between social economy enterprises and traditional enterprises. It also provides validated recommendations to support this kind of cooperation.

COSME **aims to** make it easier for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to access finance in all phases of their lifecycle – creation, expansion, or business transfer

INNOVFIN EU Finance for innovators Programme aims to facilitate and accelerate access to finance for innovative businesses and other innovative entities in Europe.

CREATIVE EUROPE loans to small and medium-sized enterprises in the cultural and creative sectors.

PROGRAMME FOR EMPLOYMENT AND SOCIAL INNOVATION (EASI). Aims to increase access to, and the availability of, microfinance for vulnerable groups who want to set up or develop their business and micro-enterprises. Builds up the institutional capacity of microcredit providers. Supports the development of social enterprises, in particular by facilitating access to finance.

EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS provides loans, guarantees, equity financing or corporate grants. Also, its support is provided by EU co-financed multi-annual programs.

EUROPEAN INVESTMENT BANK <https://www.eib.org/en/>

EUROPEAN INVESTMENT FUNDS <https://www.eif.org/>

Workshop: Fundraising and income generation

Thanks to this activity, participants will be able to understand how fundraising needs to be organised to succeed not only in terms of raising money but also in maximizing the mission of a firm.

There are a lot of methods that can be used for fundraising, but there is no right answer regarding which method will work best for any given country, culture, situation or business. The fundraising process is highly interactive.

Purpose

To understand how fundraising needs to be organised

Choosing the best method of fundraising according to specific situations

Time

1.5 hours

Target groups

Youth workers, young people

15-20 participants, 3-4 persons in each group

Objectives

Plan and prepare steps for fundraising

Plan a fundraising strategy

Prepare the necessary communication materials

Materials

- Classroom/training room with PCs
- Paper, pencils
- Templates for SWOT analysis and leaflet guideline
- Handout 1: Some of the most important fundraising sources
- Handout 2: Communication appeal letter

Facilitation steps

Part I (SWOT to get READY) (30 min)

Identify your business features and potentials.

Write down what you believe are the strengths, the weaknesses, the opportunities and the threats of your business in order to reach an investor easier.

TIP: could be used the Business Idea model

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... • ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... • ...
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... • ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... • ...

Part II (Identify Fundraising and Income Sources) (30 min)

Instructor's guidelines The Swot Analysis of trainees should be taken under consideration before moving to this part, in order to avoid misunderstandings.

Steps for Trainees:

1. Collecting data about the different ways of Fundraising and Income Generation
2. Identify the key elements/features of these types of funding

Based on the Key Points of the Swot Analysis, participants will select the optimum way for Fundraising and Income Generation

Part III (Communication Material) (30 min)

It is very important for a founder to develop the relevant communication material, in order to go through a successful fundraising round.

These materials will be used to introduce the company to potential investors, materials for the founder to send to investors that show more details about the strategy financially and execution-wise and, lastly, materials that show the current equity structure between founders.

It would be significant for a founder to try to optimize the materials to be concise and address key issues to communicate his story. In general, there are many different opinions regarding what constitutes the ideal set of materials for fundraising

Steps:

- Let's think that the framework below is your company's one-page leaflet, and you have to write it thoroughly and qualitatively.
- It is recommended to use your PCs to have better results
- Be precise and professional

LOGO HERE

Key information about your business (contact information)

NAME.....

ADDRESS.....

ZIP.....

EMAIL.....

PHONE.....

Image here

Image here

The purpose of the one-page leaflet in 3 sentences.

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Methods

Group activity

Reflection

Debriefing

What are the key learning points to remember about fundraising and income generation?

References

Handout 1: Some of the most important fundraising sources

1. Friends & family

It could make sense that in markets where the entrepreneurs are not going to be able to raise the amount of money that they would actually want and need upfront, one way of “hedging” the beginning of conversation regarding the fundraising procedures is by articulating their requested amount this way; “It would be obvious to ask for funding from friends and family, but shortly after them come angels or people of high net worth who are willing to invest in your startup in exchange for equity” (Espinal, 2015).

2. High-net-worth individuals

So, as we mentioned above there are people who are willing to invest in a founder’s startup or business or company in exchange for equity. There are many types of business investors. Some of them are just individuals investing out of their own pockets, while others are venture capitalists or business angels, who also name themselves as angel clubs or business associations such as crowdfunding platforms such as AngelList etc, banks, and personal investors (Root, G., 2017).

3. Government funding

“A government grant is a financial award given by the federal, state or local government to an eligible grantee with no expectation that the funds will be paid back” (Entrepreneur Staff). Government grants don’t usually include technical or other financial assistance, such as a loan or loan guarantee, an interest rate subsidy, direct appropriation, or revenue sharing. “Government grants fund business ideas and projects providing public services and stimulating the economy. Grants support critical recovery initiatives, innovative research and other programs” (Investopedia definition).

4. Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is one way that entrepreneurs can seek money and look for capital to start up their businesses, finance a new product or a project or expand their operations. Crowdfunding is based on the Internet without any mediator for supporting firms or other organizations in order to raise money directly from individuals and multiple people. This new type of fundraising emerged after the 2008 financial crisis. This came as a response to the difficulties which entrepreneurs and businesses were facing at their first stage in generating funding, as it was very difficult to raise money through the old traditional ways, for example. a bank loan. Nowadays, crowdfunding has won a lot of interest and entrepreneurs become more and more familiar with this formation of raising funds. What matters is that crowdfunding uses the power of technology, especially social media, to 61 | Page market the idea, raise funds, and hold entrepreneurs accountable.

Definition of Crowdfunding:

Crowdfunding is by definition “the practice of funding a project or a venture by raising many small amounts of money from a large number of individuals, typically via the Internet, as well as social media” (Prive, 2012; Mollick, 2014).

Investor Trading Academy: What is crowdfunding? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y6dKoWlJif4>

Handout 2: Communication appeal letter

Writing your appeal letter is a crucial procedure. Good appeal letters always tell a personal story, expressing the need that a founder wants to raise funds. In other words, it could be called a document or even better a one-page leaflet. The main purpose of this one-page leaflet is to tempt the potential investor to want to learn more about what a founder is doing. In other words, founders have to define their goal and share their mission with the least amount of information possible, as at the first stage, an investor’s attention is to learn some specific things as he/she can deal with a lot of options available to them (Garecht, 2017).

The one-page leaflet should be:

- Formal and of high quality. It is common sense that ugly or dirty leaflets will not stand out.
- Readable from any device, such as smartphones and tablets, which makes sense as most people will be on the go and the usage of these kinds of devices is often.
- Both informative and synoptic at the same time.

The one-page leaflet could start with all the key information about the founder’s firm, some images and some contact information that will likely be the founder’s calling card when others introduce him/her. A founder has to know that the one-page document will be communicated and distributed to the general public, including the competitors. In addition, while a founder wants it to be informative, he/she could make a video or a short movie instead of just a presentation.

Other Resources

Forbes: The Ultimate Pitch Deck to Raise Money for Startups, available at: <http://bit.ly/2oDGYIA>

Mody, L. (2015). Venture Capital 101: A Crash Course, available at:

<https://startupsventurecapital.com/venture-capital-101-a-crash-course-ed80b0d87bd5>

VIDEO: TheWFEAcademy: 3 Tips to Approach Angel Investors

www.youtube.com/watch?v=pPwv7z5d0P0

Business Funding Show Twitter: @bizfundingshow www.businessfundingshow.com/advice/list-of-top-crowdfunding-platforms/

Workshops about social entrepreneurship

https://ied.eu/entre_files/outcomes/Workshops_about_social_entrepreneurship.pdf

Resources

Further reading

Access to finance. (2021). Your Europe. https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/finance-funding/getting-funding/access-finance/index_en.htm

Microfinance and Social Entrepreneurship axis of EaSI. (n.d.). European Commission.

<https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1084&langId=en>

Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, (2019). Social Business Initiative (SBI) follow up: Cooperation between social economy enterprises and traditional

enterprises. European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/growth/content/social-business-initiative-sbi-follow-cooperation-between-social-economy-enterprises-and_en

Video materials

Financing Options for Small Businesses: Crash Course Entrepreneurship #16

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MYVL1XHeB74>

Startup Funding Explained: Everything You Need to Know

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=677ZtSMr4-4>

Startup funding stages explained: from angel round to Series A

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tk5Zv6WITDo>

Module 11. Measuring performance

Introduction

“What gets measured, gets done”. Managing performance is an important part of running any professional business. It can be challenging to evaluate the performance, but it is imperative in order to have a successful business. It offers a way to ensure that the employees can contribute meaningfully to the company’s success and make it prosper. For managers, measurements help communicate strategic goals, gain inside into current performance, and make improvements and organizational change. For employees, having performance measures help clarify success criteria in their jobs. Also, it can increase motivation to perform and self-esteem.

As a consequence, this section gives information about:

- Characteristics of measuring performance;
- Tools to apply measuring performance.

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to:

- Describe measuring performance;
- Explain the importance of measuring performance;
- Give examples of tools for measuring performance.

Duration

This section will last 4 hours including both the theoretical part and the workshop. The theoretical part explains the action of measuring performance in a business and exemplifies such tools. The practical part helps the participants to create a personal development plan.

An overview of measuring performance

Performance measurement is a numerical result of an analysis that shows how successfully an organization is accomplishing its goals. When you measure your employees' performance properly, you may spot operational flaws and encourage them to contribute more at work. Employee performance assessments can also aid in the identification of candidates for leadership roles and other chances for promotion.

Measuring performance is an important aspect of tracking a company's growth and success. It comprises comparing a company's actual performance to its stated objectives. Checking your business's performance regularly safeguards your company against financial and organizational challenges. It aids firms in reducing process costs, increasing productivity and enhancing mission effectiveness.

Tools for measuring performance

Balanced Scorecard (BSC)

One of the most commonly used frameworks for measuring Business Performance is the Balanced Scorecard because it offers the possibility to be customized to any organization. The Balanced Scorecard is a framework used to make sure that all necessary perspectives for managers and executives are covered within the organization when measuring performance:

- *Financial* – reflect the profitability, growth, and shareholder value that the company brings
- *Customer* – find out how the customer perceives the value that the company creates
- *Innovation & Learning and Perspective* – focus on what to do in the company to make it stay competitive.
- *Internal Business perspective* – consider the operations run by the company that improves customer satisfaction (employee skills, quality, and productivity in the company, core competences, market leadership, special technology the company possesses)

Key performance indicators (KPIs)

A set of measurable statistics used to judge a company's overall long-term performance is referred to as key performance indicators (KPIs). They are used to determine a company's strategic, financial, and operational accomplishments, especially when compared to those of other companies in the same industry. Key performance indicators measure a company's success versus a set of targets, objectives, or industry peers.

One of the most basic examples of a KPI is Revenue Per Client (RPC). For example, if you generate \$100,000 in revenue annually and you have 100 clients, then your RPC is \$1,000.

There are some types of key performance indicators:

- **Financial Metrics:** typically focus on revenue and profit margins.
- **Customer Metrics:** generally, focus on per-customer efficiency, customer satisfaction, and customer retention.
- **Process Performance Metrics:** aim to measure and monitor operational performance across the organization.

A good KPI provides objective and clear information on progress towards an end goal. Also, it tracks and measures factors such as efficiency, quality, timeliness, and performance and it provides a way to measure performance over time.

360-Degree Feedback

360-degree feedback is also known as full-circle appraisal, multi-rater feedback, multi-source feedback, upwards feedback, group performance review, 360-degree appraisal, 540-degree feedback, all-round feedback, and peer appraisal. This is the feedback process which involves collecting perceptions about a person's behaviour and the impact of that behaviour from the person's boss or bosses, direct reports, colleagues, fellow members of project teams, internal and external customers, and suppliers.

The information collected through 360-degree feedback divides the information which is gathered into three groups such as style, knowledge and individual skills. There are introduced two types of feedback results expected and unexpected results. Also, 360-degree feedback implements as self-development, highlighting training needs, team-building, performance appraisal, strategic development and remuneration. Furthermore, it represents a multisource approach to achieving business strategy, supporting cultural change, fostering individual development, enhancing team effectiveness, and identifying training and selection requirements.

Personal development plans (PDP)

A personal development plan (PDP) is a formal record of the abilities an employee possesses and those that they need to improve. It's a framework for them to think about what they want to achieve and how to get there. Moreover, it is a source of discovery, inspiration, and drive for employees.

PDPs can serve as the foundation for performance evaluations for managers. They can serve as a guide rope to keep students focused on progress while also informing general aims and objectives. The PDP provides them with a goal to strive for, whether it's a certification, a new skill, or a promotion. Keep the PDP at the centre of your motivating approach since managers are judged on how successfully their people fulfil their goals. It motivates your employees to seek out opportunities to learn new things, study, and grow.

Performance appraisals

The phrase "performance assessment" refers to the process of evaluating an employee's work performance and overall contribution to the company regularly. A performance assessment, also known as an annual review, performance review or evaluation, or employee appraisal, assesses an employee's abilities, accomplishments, and progress, or lack thereof.

Companies utilize performance assessments to provide employees with broad feedback on their work, as well as to justify salary raises, incentives, and termination choices. They can be done at any time; however, they are most commonly done annually, semi-annually, or quarterly.

Human resources (HR) departments frequently create performance assessments as a tool for workers to advance in their careers. Individuals receive feedback on their work performance from them. It ensures that employees are managing and reaching the expectations placed on them, as well as providing assistance on how to achieve those goals if they fall short.

Reward and recognition programs

Employee recognition programs include various activities that employers take to recognize, appreciate and reward their employees for good work. Employee recognition programs are often combined with rewards. That is why, instead of just "Recognition" programs, we see companies implementing "Rewards & Recognition" programs.

Employee recognition software is the technology that enables people to manage abstract human notions, like employee happiness and relationships, with the same purpose and efficiency as project deadlines and sales targets. Employee recognition tools, in the hands of smart peers and managers, may improve the corporate culture.

Some examples of useful programs and recognition software are Nectar, Assembly, Bonusly, Kazoo, WeGift and Awardco.

Workshop: My personal development tree

Purpose

This activity aims to create a personal development plan for each trainee.

Time

60 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young entrepreneurs

Objectives

Identify long-term goals

Identify short-term goals

Identify the steps needed to reach a goal, possible obstacles and needed resources

Create SMART goals

Materials

- Paper, pens
- Tree template (model)

Facilitation steps

1. Introduction (5 min)

Task: Ask the participants to draw a large tree that includes the roots, trunk, major branches, smaller branches, leaves, flowers and thorns.

Tips and tricks: Show them a model drawing.

2. Theoretical part (10 min)

Explain

Explain that the growth of a tree is like the growth and development of a person.

The parts of the tree represent the following:

- Roots: their values and skills
- Trunk: areas in their lives that give them strength – friends, family, church, mosque, workplace
- Branches: goals in the near future (what they want to do or accomplish soon)
- Thorns: obstacles they might meet along the way
- Leaves: resources that they will need to reach goals (people, information)
- Flowers: goals in the far away future or future achievements

Add extra information about goals (branches and flowers)

Goals – where people want to reach or what they want to accomplish.

The goals should be SMART:

Goals should be SMART	Examples that cannot be reached	Examples that can be reached
Specific	I will be rich	I will earn 5,000 EUR/month
Measurable	I will attend Saturday classes	I will attend Saturday classes
Achievable	I will become president of the Philippines by next year	I will become president of the young group in our barangay by next year

Realistic	I will become a player of one of the famous Philippines Basketball Association teams	I will play basketball with the basketball team in our barangay
Time-framed	I will find a construction job	I will find a construction job in the next 2 months

In order to reach a goal, follow the following steps:

Set goal, Make a plan, Get to work, Stick to it, Reach goal

Ask them: What do you think you will need to do to reach one of your goals (in one of the branches)?

3. Practice activity (25 min)

Individual activity

Task: Ask participants to label their trees with their own information.

Tips and tricks:

- Remind the meaning of the parts of the tree
- Label the tree parts together, asking a volunteer to come up with who can be a model. As you do the roots, for example, have everyone do their roots in their handbooks.

4. Wrap up (15 min)

Form groups of 2-3 people.

Task: Use the information on their own trees and choose one goal (one per learner). A goal that you want to achieve 1 year from now. Identify the steps to reach the goal.

Tips and tricks:

- Remember them about SMART goals and the steps to reach a goal.
- If participants are not comfortable writing, they can draw pictures or symbols that represent their goals and then explain them to their partner or the group.

5. Evaluation (10 min)

Bring everyone together.

Task:

Invite 2-3 pairs to share the goal that they worked on and the steps that they identified to reach that goal.

Discuss together: How do you think what you learned today can help you plan for your work in the future? For your career in the future?

Methods

Individual work

Group discussion

Debriefing

What is the personal development plan good for?

References

Life Skills: Learning, Working, Serving – https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/FM_Module-1-Personal-Development-1.pdf

Resources

Further reading

Likierman, S. A. (2007). Guide to key performance indicators. Communicating the measures that matter, Price Water House Coopers. https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/audit-services/corporate-reporting/assets/pdfs/uk_kpi_guide.pdf

Baroudi, R. (2014). Key performance indicators, Performance, Volume 6. https://www.academia.edu/31315614/EY_Performance_Key_performance_indicators

Putter, M. (2021). What is a personal development plan?. CPD Online College Knowledge base. <https://cpdonline.co.uk/knowledge-base/business/what-are-personal-development-plans/>

Better workplaces Better world (2021). What You Need to Know About Performance Appraisals.

<https://www.shrm.org/resourcesandtools/tools-and-samples/need-to-know/pages/what-you-need-to-know-about-performance-appraisals.aspx>

Vantage Circle (2022). 50 Rewards And Recognition Ideas To Boost Employee Recognition.

<https://blog.vantagecircle.com/rewards-and-recognition-ideas/>

Eisalou, M. R. (2014), Human Resource 360-Degree Feedback, LLP LAMBERT Academic Publicat.

<https://www.arabianjbm.com/pdfs/books/5.pdf>

Video materials

Performance Reviews | Performance Evaluations & Appraisal

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KcGhX7Htk9U>

How Do You Measure Your Business Performance? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C2lggnjP12E>

Individual Development Plans - self-managed by employees

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kJSTcNdRpeM>

Module 12. Marketing strategies

Introduction

In this module, you will be introduced to content marketing. You will be able to define what content marketing is and explain why it is important in today's market. The ultimate goal of a marketing strategy is to achieve and communicate a sustainable competitive advantage over rival companies by understanding the needs and wants of its consumers. You will discover the purpose of what content should be able to do and what makes content effective. You will discover the importance of how your own professional brand can play in the importance of your company's content marketing strategy and you will build your own professional brand.

As a consequence, this section gives information about:

- Marketing strategies;
- The five components of marketing strategies;
- Examples of marketing strategies.

Competences

On completion of this module, participants will be able to:

- Define marketing strategy;
- Explain the components of marketing strategy;
- Give examples of marketing strategies.

Duration

This section will last 4 hours including both the theoretical part and the workshop. The theoretical part explains the concept of marketing strategy and its components. The practical part helps the participants to realise a marketing strategy.

An overview of marketing strategy

A marketing strategy refers to a business's overall game plan for reaching prospective consumers and turning them into customers of their products or services. Marketing strategies should revolve around a company's value proposition, which communicates to consumers what the company stands for, how it operates, and why it deserves its business.

The marketing strategy is outlined in the marketing plan, which is a document that details the specific types of marketing activities a company conducts and contains timetables for rolling out various marketing initiatives. In other words, marketing strategies cover big-picture messaging, while marketing plans delineate the logistical details of specific campaigns.

An entrepreneurial marketing strategy is an idea, plan, or other means that a business owner uses to advertise their product or service. It enables the company to be successful and succeed in making more sales while still making a profit.

The 5 P's of marketing

The 5 P's of marketing – Product, Price, Promotion, Place, and People – are key marketing elements used to position a business strategically. They are variables that managers and owners control to satisfy

customers in their target market, add value to their business, and help differentiate their business from competitors.

The next table explains what are the 5 P's of marketing and gives example how Netflix is applying it:

5P	EXPLANATION	EXAMPLE
Product	Product refers to the products and services offered by a business. Product decisions include function, packaging, appearance, warranty, quality, etc.	Netflix offers its customers an extensive list of programmes e.g. features films, TV shows, documentaries, Netflix originals and many more. Netflix adds new TV programmes and movies every week to meet the growing demands of the subscribers.
Price	Price refers to the pricing strategy for products and services and how it will affect customers. Pricing decisions do not include just the selling price, but also discounts, payment arrangements, credit terms, and any price-matching services offered.	Customers pay a monthly subscription. They can choose from three plans which have different prices.
Promotion	Promotion refers to the activities that make the business more known to consumers. It includes items such as sponsorships, advertising, and public relations activities.	Netflix uses almost all media channels to promote itself and that too through the content it offers. Netflix's first-month free trial policy is also a promotional activity to persuade potential customers to subscribe and use its services.
Place	Place refers to where the product/service of the business is seen, made, sold, or distributed. In essence, place decisions are associated with distribution channels and ways of getting the product to targeted key customers.	Netflix is available virtually anywhere and anytime.
People	People refer to the staff, salespeople, and those who work for the business.	Since Netflix conducts its operations mainly on online platforms, the company's marketing team and social media team form the most important arm of the organization.

These are the key factors that are involved in the marketing of a good or service. The 5 P's can be used when planning a new business venture, evaluating an existing offer, or trying to optimize sales with a target audience. It can also be used to test a current marketing strategy on a new audience.

Examples of marketing strategies

Content marketing

Content marketing is a marketing strategy used to attract, engage, and retain an audience by creating and sharing relevant articles, videos, podcasts, infographics, and paid ads. This approach establishes expertise, promotes brand awareness, and keeps your business top of mind when it's time to buy what you sell.

Example: A restaurant writes a blog post about how to plan a menu for a graduation party in the spring.

Social media marketing

Social media marketing (SMM) uses social media and social networks—like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram—to market products and services, engage with existing customers, and reach new ones. Social media marketing has transformed the way businesses are able to influence consumer behaviour—from promoting content that drives engagement to extract personal data that makes messaging resonate with users.

Example: Clear, who connected with social media influencer and popular soccer player Cristiano Ronaldo: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CUdH9fErUqu/?hl=en>

Email marketing

Email marketing is a powerful marketing channel, a form of direct marketing as well as digital marketing, that uses email to promote your business's products or services. It can help make your customers aware of your latest items or offers by integrating them into your marketing automation efforts. It can also play a pivotal role in your marketing strategy with lead generation, brand awareness, building relationships or keeping customers engaged between purchases through different types of marketing emails.

Example: Personalization – from the timing of the email (birthday) to the personalized salutation (“Happy birthday, Carry!”).

Referral marketing

Referral marketing is when you get your customers to tell their friends about you. Like any marketing, referral marketing (also known as word-of-mouth marketing) usually happens organically. Humans are, by nature, social creatures. We naturally share our experiences with our friends.

Example: Revolut – Each campaign can offer different cash rewards for each referred-in friend.

Event sponsoring

An event sponsor is a company that supports an event, usually by providing funds, in exchange for something valuable. Oftentimes this “something valuable” comes in the form of increased brand exposure, access to attendee data, speaking opportunities at the event, or discounted event tickets.

Example: An event isn't complete without food. Delectable meals can indeed elevate the attendee experience. You can even boost everyone's interest by offering free food. Therefore, it's essential to find a food sponsor for your next big event.

Influencer marketing

Influencer marketing involves a brand collaborating with an online influencer to market one of its products or services. Some influencer marketing collaborations are less tangible than that – brands simply work with influencers to improve brand recognition.

Example: Dunkin' Donuts made a special offer on National Donut Day, and Collab selected lifestyle creators to spread content about the offer in their cities on SnapChat. They chose eight popular influencers to create and distribute teaser content. The eight influencers then "took over" the Dunkin' Donuts SnapChat channel on National Donut Day. The result was that Dunkin' Donuts gained ten times more followers on their SnapChat channel on National Donut Day than they usually did in a month.

Promotions

Promotion belongs to the 5Ps of marketing. It's all about strategies and techniques that help communicate a product to the audience. The goal of promotions is to present your product, increase demand, and differentiate it. So, promotion is the basic element of marketing.

Example: "Red Bull Gives You Wings," the company's famous tagline, is used in a majority of their advertisements, which are most often shared digitally or on TV and streaming services.

Offering refunds

A refund usually means getting your money back when you return something you bought. You return the product because you don't want it. Sometimes, rather than giving money, the seller may either give you a replacement item or a voucher. In most cases, the voucher is only usable at that store. A voucher is a piece of paper that entitles the holder to a free product, service, or discount.

Example: Because the rental car agency ran out of cars, the customer gets a refund.

Customer loyalty programs

A customer loyalty program is an e-commerce marketing strategy that rewards loyal customers who frequently engage with a brand. Customer loyalty programs are designed to incentivize repeat purchases by providing membership discounts, unique offers, VIP events, and more.

Example: Sephora customer loyalty program is Beauty Insider where members can earn one point for every dollar they spend in the store and climb the ladder from "insider" to "VIB" and to "rouge".

Workshop: Market your business

Purpose

This activity aims to help the trainees create a marketing strategy.

Time

90 minutes

Target groups

Youth workers, young entrepreneurs

Objectives

Create a marketing strategy

Prepare a specific marketing strategy

Argue the impact of a marketing strategy

Materials

- Video projector
- Printed templates
- Pens

Facilitation steps

1. Introduction (5 min)

Task: Which advertising is catchier? Why?

Skittles

Source: <https://youtu.be/RWuev4LlO9g>

Coca Cola

Nike

Tips and tricks: Discuss with the trainees what makes an advertisement catch the public. Ask them to give examples of other advertisements that they like.

2. Theoretical part (15 min)

Explain: Marketing strategy

3. Practice activity (50 min)

Groups of 4-5 people

Each group has a Marketing strategy template

Task: Complete the marketing strategy template. Complete the next sections:

- Background;
- Market;
- Target audience;
- Competition;
- Offering;
- Messages;
- Sales and buying process;
- Pricing;
- Communication & promotion.

Tips and tricks: the trainers can choose only some sections to be filled in. The trainees can choose whatever business they want to develop.

4. Wrap up (10 min)

Keep the groups from the previous activity

Task: Simulate your marketing strategy (ex: simulate a post on social media, an email to your customers, a podcast etc.)

5. Evaluation (10 min)

Bring everyone together

Task: Present your strategy marketing simulation to the whole class.

Tips and tricks: Kindly ask the trainees to give feedback on each marketing strategy.

Methods

Project-based learning

Debriefing

What are the conditions/factors that you need to consider in creating your marketing strategy?

References

Marketing strategy template – <https://images.template.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/09060450/Marketing-Strategy-Template.pdf>

Resources

Further reading

Bernardo. (2022). interObservers. <https://interobservers.com/marketing-mix-5-ps-of-marketing/>

Yildirim, H. (2022). The 5Ps of Marketing – everything you need to know to achieve success. User Guiding. <https://userguiding.com/blog/the-5-ps-of-marketing/>

Whalley, A. (2010). Strategic Marketing. Bookboon.com. <https://library.ku.ac.ke/wp-content/downloads/2011/08/Bookboon/Strategy/strategic-marketing.pdf>

Macarthy, A. (2017). 500 social media marketing tips: essential advice, hints and strategy for business: Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, Google+, YouTube, Instagram, LinkedIn, and more!. <https://www.pdfdrive.com/500-social-media-marketing-tips-essential-advice-hints-and-strategy-for-business-facebook-twitter-pinterest-google-youtube-instagram-linkedin-and-more-d194976062.html>

Artun, O & Levin, D. (2015). Predictive Marketing. Wiley. <https://www.pdfdrive.com/predictive-marketing-easy-ways-every-marketer-can-use-customer-analytics-and-big-data-d158028018.html>

Video materials

How to develop an effective marketing strategy <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=auRTKgS1bTM>

4 Marketing Strategy Principles - My Template for Marketing Anything <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gNAE8g2tytA>

How to Sell Anything: Crash Course Entrepreneurship #12 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n7-wsGLc1js&list=PL8dPuualjXtNamNkW5qIS-nKgA0on7Qze&index=13>

Evaluation

The assessment of course participants' competences may be done in several ways. The assessment method depends on whether the course is being delivered face-to-face or online, asynchronous, or synchronous, in small groups or MOOC format. It may also depend on the characteristics of the participants.

It is worth mentioning that, besides the role in evaluating participants' learning, the assessment is part of the learning process. Thus, while engaging in the evaluation, participants learn during the assessment and while analysing the feedback. Some of the assessment methods are described in the paragraphs below.

Firstly, the assessment part may be covered by some self-evaluation multiple choice questions (MCQ) through an online platform. This means that learners may have the chance to guide and evaluate themselves without the interference of any outer directive.

Multiple choice items represent a written assessment which may be used to test factual recall, levels of understanding, and ability to apply participants' learning (analysing and evaluating). A multiple-choice item consists of a stem and several possible alternative responses. These specific multiple-choice items usually consist of one main sentence, several distractors and only one correct answer. The EnMind course includes 38 multiple-choice questions (MCQs) with three answers of which only one is correct. Participants may be invited to answer a number of questions from the question bank (e.g. 10, 20, 30 or 38 questions). In the EnMind MOOC Course, the course managers opted for a 10-question assessment, selected randomly from the 38-MCQ database. In the MOOC format, the answers are shuffled automatically.

Secondly, self-assessment lets learners consider their decisions, reflect on actions and consider/plan future processes. Self-assessments carry several benefits for both learners and trainers:

- Encourage learners to take more responsibility for learning
- Are a highly effective critical thinking exercise
- Promote a deep understanding of content topics and learning styles
- Learners are usually honest in the assessment of their own performance and that of their peers

In the EnMind MOOC course, self-assessment is encouraged through forum/self-reflection questions, where participants may think critically and answer based on their knowledge, experience and skills. While reading the reflections from others, participants may be able to round their knowledge and change their attitudes/mindset in the right direction. The self-assessment method may not only be used online but also face-to-face, especially upon completing workshop activities.

Thirdly, peer evaluation is the process where learners/participants give feedback on the performance of other learners/participants. This assessment format emphasizes skills, encourages involvement, focuses on learning, provides feedback and fosters attendance. This process may be practised by using a list of questions. The focus should be on the answers or outcomes of the activities. The peer evaluation may be used online and face-to-face. In the EnMind MOOC course version, the participants are invited to comment on the forum self-reflections of others. The method is also specific to the face-to-face version, where participants may evaluate the workshop contributions of one or more of their colleagues.

Fourthly, performance-based assessment is an evaluation method which requires a learner to create an answer or a product that demonstrates his or her knowledge or skills. Performance-based assessment measures learners' ability to apply the skills and knowledge learned during the course

modules. Typically, the task challenges students to use their higher-order thinking skills to create a product or complete a process. Examples of performance assessments include:

- Group projects enable several learners to work together on a complex problem that requires planning, research, internal discussion, and group presentation
- Experiments testing how well learners understand specific concepts and can apply these in the real-world environment
- Demonstrations give learners opportunities to show their mastery of subject-area content and procedures.

In the EnMind course, the performance-based assessment is employed in several workshops which are specific to face-to-face activities.

The set of multiple-choice questions covering all EnMind course modules is provided below.

Evaluation quizzes

- 1) What definition indicates an intrapreneur?
 - a) Someone that creates a business, increases shareholder value, develops customer networks, determines potential markets
 - b) Someone who is tasked with an innovative idea or project, to enhance existing goods and services within the context of an already existing business
 - c) Someone who creates a new product, ideas, methods never made before, new iterations on products already created
- 2) Which features belong to an entrepreneur?
 - a) A starter, an individual who creates something new, a challenger
 - b) An initiator, driven by profit, good at delegating tasks
 - c) Accountable, responsible, wealthy
- 3) What is the distinguishing feature of a social enterprise?
 - a) Achieves and increases profit
 - b) Expands the business
 - c) Improves the quality of life by aiming at social change
- 4) What is the social economy?
 - a) A branch of the economy aiming at social change
 - b) A branch of economics that focuses on the relationship between social behaviour and economics
 - c) A branch of the economy that pays attention to the social consequences of economic activities
- 5) What is a social enterprise?
 - a) An organization, specifically a business or a difficult and important plan that will earn money
 - b) A business that blends revenue development and profit with the obligation to respect and assist its environment and stakeholder network
 - c) A business of buying and selling goods and services on the internet, or a particular company that does this
- 6) What are the SDGs?
 - a) A collection of interlinked goals designed to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all
 - b) Sustainable development guidelines
 - c) Goals to promote the individual development of each country

- 7) The triple bottom-line sustainability-based accounting method focuses on?
 - a) Possibilities, people, projects
 - b) Projects, profit, pollution
 - c) People, profit, planet
- 8) What is the aim of social enterprises?
 - a) Providing goods and services
 - b) Helping people in need
 - c) Concentrating only on profit issues in business
- 9) Which one is among entrepreneurial competences?
 - a) Strict work plans
 - b) Working alone
 - c) Learning through experience
- 10) How does the Market Connection Model work as a business model?
 - a) Sells business support to its target population
 - b) Provides employment opportunities and job training to clients
 - c) Provides services to clients to help them access markets
- 11) Which explanation is correct for SWOT Analysis?
 - a) It is action-oriented
 - b) It includes a competitive mindset
 - c) It includes a collaborative mindset
- 12) A business idea is:
 - a) A type of arrangement for financial investment
 - b) A concise and accurate explanation of a company's essential operations
 - c) The eagerness to do something new and clever, despite all risks
- 13) A good method for creating a business idea is to:
 - a) Start with yourself, thinking that you are a customer too
 - b) Try each idea you have
 - c) Apply all the suggestions you heard about
- 14) In order to survey your local business area:
 - a) Find out what types of businesses are already operating in your area and see if you can identify any gaps in the market
 - b) Ask your family and friends about the things they would like to find that are not locally available
 - c) Think about business ideas by considering all the resources and institutions in your area (such as natural resources, characteristics and skills of people in the local community, waste products etc.)
- 15) Business simulation games help entrepreneurs to:
 - a) Make their own business more like games - interesting or enjoyable
 - b) Gain knowledge or a piece of information obtained by studying
 - c) Enhance their management and organizational abilities
- 16) What is a business model?
 - a) A high-level plan for profitably operating a business in a specific marketplace
 - b) The way how a business is managed
 - c) Any plan in a business structure

- 17) How many types of business models exist?
- Two types of business models: Business to Business and Business to Consumer
 - There are as many types of business models as there are types of businesses
 - Internet retail and brick-and-mortar stores
- 18) What is a Freemium Business Model?
- Free access to online applications
 - Free access to a given service with the possibility of purchasing additional functionalities
 - Freeware that works only on iOS Mobile Phones
- 19) How does business model innovation improve business performance?
- Innovation can help you anticipate market changes more quickly and get ahead of opportunities
 - Innovation is the leading force of competitiveness
 - Innovation helps you take advantage of new technologies
- 20) The Social Business Model Canvas is described as:
- A particular model for arranging information or images in a document that you can copy and use for your own purposes
 - A list of planned activities or things to be done showing the times or dates when they are intended to happen or be done
 - A graphical depiction of a company's business model, defining how the organization develops, delivers and collects value
- 21) The mission of the Social Business Model Canvas answers the next question:
- What change are you planning to make in the world?
 - How much surplus do you expect to create each year?
 - How will you get out to your target customers?
- 22) In order to create a social business model canvas, you have to:
- Start with defining the value proposition for a specific customer segment
 - Focus more on finances: cost of delivery, community reinvestment, revenue streams
 - Fill the canvas in a specific order, from left to right
- 23) What is a "social business model fast track"?
- A business plan based on a needs analysis
 - It is a three-question model
 - A business model that cuts down bureaucracy
- 24) What is a "Social business model long path"?
- A business model that takes care of the bureaucracy
 - A business model based on a needs analysis
 - A social business model that combines elements derived from different business model templates
- 25) What is a Social Business Model Canvas?
- A tool that helps to plan, communicate and refine a business model in a simple, visual way
 - A template that shows real value to customers
 - A powerful digital design tool that can be used in education to create projects
- 26) What are the main parts of a Social Business Model Canvas?
- Mission, implementation, value, market and finances
 - Mission, implementation, product design, distribution

- c) Mission, product, price, place and promotion
- 27) What types of financing are available for those who want to start a business?
- Starters funding, experts funding, business funding investors
 - Pre-seed funding, seed funding, series A, B funding, European funding
 - Seed funding, start-up funding, European funding
- 28) The decision to provide EU financing will be made by...
- European investment funds
 - Local financial institutions such as banks, venture capitalists or angel investors
 - Private investors
- 29) Which elements do you need in order to launch a social enterprise?
- Share capital, connections, business
 - Funding rounds, business, investors
 - Investors, funding, business plan
- 30) Who are the most common pre-seed funders?
- Funders themselves, friends, families
 - Businessmen, investors, shareholders
 - Families, partners, investors
- 31) What is measuring performance?
- Making one thing the same as others of that type or comparing one thing to something accepted as a model
 - Separating people or things into different levels of quality, size, importance, etc.
 - A numerical result of an analysis that shows how successfully an organization is accomplishing its goals
- 32) Key performance indicators measure:
- A company's success versus a set of targets, objectives, or industry peers
 - The part of existence that is measured in minutes, days, years, etc
 - A student's piece of work
- 33) What is a personal development plan?
- A collage of images and words representing a person's wishes or goals, intended to serve as inspiration or motivation
 - A formal record of the abilities an employee possesses and those that they need to improve
 - A qualification that someone receives when they are successful in a course
- 34) Choose the option that exemplifies only tools for measuring performance:
- Balanced scorecard, performance appraisals and recognition programs
 - 360 – degree feedback, standardized test, surveys
 - Key performance indicators, interviews, reward
- 35) What is a marketing strategy?
- The activity of marketing products and services by communicating directly with consumers by phone, mail, or on the internet
 - A business's overall game plan for reaching prospective consumers and turning them into customers of their products or services
 - A form of advertising by which the customer can reply to show interest in a product or service, by filling in a form, phoning a number, sending an email, etc.
- 36) Which are the 5Ps of marketing?

- a) Product, Price, Promotion, Place, People
- b) Product, Page, Partner, Place, Promotion
- c) Product, Percent, Promotion, Place, Performance

37) What is referral marketing?

- a) A company that supports an event, usually by providing funds, in exchange for something valuable
- b) A powerful marketing channel, a form of direct marketing as well as digital marketing, that uses email to promote your business's products or services
- c) When you get your customers to tell their friends about you

38) Which one does not represent an example of a marketing strategy?

- a) Influencer marketing
- b) Promotions
- c) Performance

*The correct answers are available in the check sheet at Appendix 1.

Self-Reflection questions

Examples for social enterprises.

Take a look at these [9 business model examples of social enterprises](#). Which one do you like most and why?

Why chose a car

Every car takes you from point A to point B. But customers choose a car because it may provide them status, a feeling of safety, low costs, and so forth. Customers are only willing to pay for the car if it provides them with the value that they are seeking. What value would you need a car to provide?

Elevate your business

Imagine you are in the elevator of the tallest building in your city, you are standing next to an investor, and both of you are going to the top floor. This means that you have 1 minute to convince him or her of your idea.

Please briefly explain your own business model using the elevator pitch technique. Answer the following questions:

- Who is your client?
- What can we offer to the client?
- How will we deliver value to the customer?
- Where we the client can find us
- Please write down your own business model

Bibliography

- Abu-Saifan, S. (February 2012: 22-27) Social Entrepreneurship: Definition and Boundaries. Technology Innovation Management Review.
- Ahmad, N.A.; Rasul, M.S.; Othman, N.; Jalaludin, N.A. (2022). Generating Entrepreneurial Ideas for Business Development. Sustainability 14, 4905. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14094905>
- Anika, H. (2018). How to Master the Business Model Canvas for Social Entrepreneurs. Tbd. <https://www.tbd.community/en/a/how-master-business-model-canvas-social-entrepreneurs>
- Annaleena Parhankangas and Michael Ehrlich. (July 2014). How Entrepreneurs Seduce BusinessAngels: An Impression Management Approach. Journal of Business Venturing. Vol. 29.4. July 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2013.08.001>.
- Artun, O & Levin, D. (2015). Predictive Marketing. Wiley. <https://www.pdfdrive.com/predictive-marketing-easy-ways-every-marketer-can-use-customer-analytics-and-big-data-d158028018.html>
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. Journal of management, 17(1), 99-120.
- Barone, A. (2022). Marketing Strategy. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/marketing-strategy.asp>
- Baroudi, R. (2014). Key performance indicators, Performance, Volume 6. https://www.academia.edu/31315614/EY_Performance_Key_performance_indicators
- Baswedan, A. (2011) One Year of Teaching, a Lifetime Inspiration. [Online] Available from: http://www.indikaenergy.co.id/03_Opening.php [Accessed: 10 May 2021]
- Bernardo. (2022). interObservers. <https://interobservers.com/marketing-mix-5-ps-of-marketing/>
- Better workplaces Better world (2021). What You Need to Know About Performance Appraisals. <https://www.shrm.org/resourcesandtools/tools-and-samples/need-to-know/pages/what-you-need-to-know-about-performance-appraisals.aspx>
- Birkholz, J. (2021). Do not judge a business idea by its cover: The relation between topics in business ideas and incorporation probability. Institute for economic research and policy. https://media.suub.uni-bremen.de/bitstream/elib/5573/4/Do%20not%20judge%20a%20business%20idea%20by%20its%20cover_Birkholz,%20ierp.pdf
- Bizzabo. (2022). The Ultimate Guide to Event Sponsorship in 2022. <https://www.bizzabo.com/blog/event-sponsorship/>
- Blank, S. (2018). The Difference Between Innovators and Entrepreneurs. ThinkGrowth. <https://thinkgrowth.org/the-difference-between-innovators-and-entrepreneurs-a430602ff8ea>
- Bornstein D. and Davis, S. (2010). Social Entrepreneurship: What Everyone Needs to Know. New York: Oxford University Press. Burkett, I. (n.d.) Using the Business Model Canvas for Social Enterprise Design. [Online] Available from: <http://www.mbs.edu/facultyresearch/apsilc/Documents/Business%20Model%20for%20SE%20DesignBurkett.pdf> [Accessed: 10 May 2021]
- Boulton, R. E. S., Libert, B. D., & Samek, S. M. (2000). 'A business model for the new economy', Journal of Business Strategy, 21(4)

- Brannback, M. & Carsrud, A. (2016). Fundamentals for becoming a successful entrepreneur: from business idea to launch and management, Paul Boger.
https://books.google.ro/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Ih_qCgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT14&dq=business+idea&ots=1wDoYDMODD&sig=Q0tRgysTh05Jy8NBavoljyqj1BM&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=business%20idea&f=false
- CFI. 5P's of Marketing. (2022). <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/knowledge/other/5-ps-marketing/>
- Clay Spinuzzi, Scott Nelson, Keela S. Thomson, Francesca Lorenzini, Rosemary A. French, Gegory Pogue, Sidney D. Burbuck, Joel Momberger. (September 2014). Making the Pitch: Examining Dialogue and Revisions in Entrepreneurs' Pitch Decks. IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication 57 no. 3, <http://hdl.handle.net/2152/25712>.
- Colin Clark. (July 2008). The Impact of Entrepreneurs' Oral 'Pitch' Presentation Skills on Business Angels' Initial Screening Investment Decisions. Venture Capital: An International Journal of Entrepreneurial Finance, 10 no. 3.
- College of Agriculture and Life Sciences Communication and Marketing. (n.d). Writing Effective Impact Statements: Who Cares? So What?.
<https://www.communications.cals.vt.edu/resources/impact-statements.html>
- Cuofano, G. (2022). What Is A SOAR Analysis And How To Use It. FourWeekMBA.
<https://fourweekmba.com/soar-analysis/>
- Deloitte Insights. (2018). The rise of the social enterprise.
https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/insights/us/articles/HCTrends2018/2018-HCTrends_Rise-of-the-social-enterprise.pdf
- Denning, P. and dunham, r. (2010.2). The Innovator's Way. MIT Press.
- Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, (2019). Social Business Initiative (SBI) follow up: Cooperation between social economy enterprises and traditional enterprises. European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/growth/content/social-business-initiative-sbi-follow-cooperation-between-social-economy-enterprises-and_en
- Dreyer, B., Lüdeke-Freund, F., Hamann, R., & Faccar, K. (2017). Upsides and downsides of the sharing economy: Collaborative consumption business models' stakeholder value impacts and their relationship to context. Technological Forecasting and Social Change
- Drip. (2022). 7 of the Best Customer Loyalty Programs You Can Copy.
<https://www.drip.com/blog/customer-loyalty-programs>
- Durant, I. (2021). What Is Entrepreneurial Marketing?. Peep Strategy Marketing Made Easy.
<https://peepstrategy.com/what-is-entrepreneurial-marketing/#:~:text=its%20marketing%20goals,-,What%20is%20an%20entrepreneurial%20marketing%20strategy%3F,while%20still%20making%20a%20profit>
- Eisalou, M. R. (2014), Human Resource 360-Degree Feedback, LLP LAMBERT Academic Publicat.
<https://www.arabianjbmr.com/pdfs/books/5.pdf>
- European Commission. (n.d.). COSME- Europe's programme for small and medium-sized enterprises.
<https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/cosme/>
- European Commission. (n.d.). Microfinance and Social Entrepreneurship axis of EaSI...
<https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1084&langId=en>

- European Commission. (n.d.). Social economy in the EU. ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/social-economy_en
- European Commission. (n.d.). Social enterprise. ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/social-economy/enterprises_en
- European Commission. Access to finance for the cultural and creative sectors. (n.d.). <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/access-finance-cultural-and-creative-sectors>
- European Commission. Accessing the funds. (n.d.). https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/index.cfm/en/funding/accessing-funds/
- Force, A. G. (2019). 9 Business Model Examples For Social Enterprises. Change Creator. <https://changecreator.com/9-business-model-examples-social-enterprises/>
- Forsberg, C. & Daleke, M. (2020). Measuring and Visualizing Business Performance Indicators in Corporate Accelerators. KTH Royal Institute of Technology School of Industrial Engineering and Management. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1460375/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Gassmann, O., Frankenberger, K., & Csik, M. (2013). The St. Gallen business model navigator.
- Geyser, W. (2022). What is Influencer Marketing? – The Ultimate Guide for 2022. Influencer Marketing Hub. <https://influencermarketinghub.com/influencer-marketing/#toc-0>
- Ghorbani, S. (2021). How much do we know about Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their origins?. Sustainable. https://thesustainablemag.com/planet/the-history-of-sustainable-development-goals-sdgs/?gclid=CjwKCAiAq8f-BRBtEiwAGr3DgYT6J5LNV59HzFdL8Un39pZhE8X3HwbHezcw_pd4dpzhyLZQxUsa9hoCYsgQAvD_BwE
- Girotra, K., & Netessine, S. (2013). OM forum—business model innovation for sustainability. *Manufacturing & Service Operations Management*, 15(4), 537-544.
- GoGreen Portland (n.d.) The Social Enterprise Business Model Canvas. [Online] Available from: [http://portland.gogreenconference.net/downloads/GGPDx_Guided_Learning_Entrepreneurship\(FRONT\).pdf](http://portland.gogreenconference.net/downloads/GGPDx_Guided_Learning_Entrepreneurship(FRONT).pdf) [Accessed: 10 May 2021]
- Graves, T. (2011) Using Business Model Canvas for non-profits. [Online] Available from: <http://weblog.tetradian.com/2011/07/16/bmcanvas-for-nonprofits/> [Accessed: 10 May 2021]
- Guy Kawasaki. (n.d.). The 10/20/30 Rule of PowerPoint. GuyKawasaki.com, https://guykawasaki.com/the_102030_rule/
- Hall, R. (1993). 'A framework linking intangible resources and capabilities to sustainable competitive advantage', *Strategic Management Journal*, 14(8)
- Hayes, A. (2021). Entrepreneur. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-entrepreneur.asp>
- Hayes, A. (2021). Entrepreneur. Investopedia. www.investopedia.com/terms/e/entrepreneur.asp
- Hayes, A. (2021). Performance Appraisal. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/what-is-a-performance-appraisal-4586834>
- Hayes, A. (2022). Social Media Marketing (SMM). Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-media-marketing-smm.asp>
- Heath, C. and Heath, d. Made to Stick. (2007). random House, 2007.3.

- Hernan Jaramillo. (January 12, 2015). 11 Hacks to Get Meetings With Investors in Silicon Valley. HackerMoon. <https://hackernoon.com/11-hacks-to-get-meetings-with-investors-in-silicon-valley-14b4851ab3e8>
- InnovFin - EU Finance for Innovators. (n.d.). European Investment Bank. <https://www.eib.org/en/products/mandates-partnerships/innovfin/index.htm>
- International Labour Organization. (2015). Generate your business idea. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/---emp_ent/---ifp_seed/documents/instructionalmaterial/wcms_436192.pdf
- Investopedia. (2021). Intrapreneur. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/intrapreneur.asp>
- Joanne Cleaver. (March 20, 2015). 3 Steps to the Perfect 3-Minute Pitch. Entrepreneur, <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/242523>
- Julie Schott. (August 7, 2015). Is Quip the Uber of Toothbrushes?. Elle. <http://www.elle.com/beauty/reviews/a29700/quip-toothbrush-subscription/>
- Kathan, W., Matzler, K., & Veider, V. (2016). The sharing economy: Your business model's friend or foe?. *Business Horizons*, 59(6), 663- 672.
- Kim, W. C. & Mauborgne, R. (2000). Knowing a winning business idea when you see one. *Harvard Business Review*. http://hse-entrepreneur.narod.ru/knowing_idea.pdf
- Kuzulu, E. (2016). Is 360 Degree Feedback Appraisal an Effective Way of Performance Evaluation?. *ResearchGate*. DOI: 10.6007/IJARBS/v6-i5/2124
- Laidre, A. (2012). Starting a Business - Define Your Value Proposition. iPlanner. https://www.iplanner.net/business-financial/online/how-to-articles.aspx?article_id=value-proposition
- Lakshmi Balachandra, Anthony Briggs, Kimberly Eddleston, and Candida Brush. (June 2013). Pitch Like a Man: Gender Stereotypes and Entrepreneur Pitch Success. *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, 33 no. 8. <http://digitalknowledge.babson.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2634&context=fer>
- Lev, B. (2000). *Intangibles: Management, Measurement, and Reporting*. Brookings Institution Press.
- Likierman, S. A. (2007). Guide to key performance indicators. Communicating the measures that matter, Price Water House Coopers. https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/audit-services/corporate-reporting/assets/pdfs/uk_kpi_guide.pdf
- Macarthy, A. (2017). 500 social media marketing tips: essential advice, hints and strategy for business : Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, Google+, YouTube, Instagram, LinkedIn, and more!. <https://www.pdfdrive.com/500-social-media-marketing-tips-essential-advice-hints-and-strategy-for-business-facebook-twitter-pinterest-google-youtube-instagram-linkedin-and-more-d194976062.html>
- Mailchimp. (2022). Content Marketing. <https://mailchimp.com/marketing-glossary/content-marketing/#:~:text=Content%20marketing%20is%20a%20marketing,to%20buy%20what%20you%20sell>
- Mailchimp. (2022). Email Marketing. <https://mailchimp.com/marketing-glossary/email-marketing/>
- Marc Andreessen. (June 25, 2007). The PMARCA Guide to Startups. Part 4: The Only Thing That Matters. Pmarchive. http://pmarchive.com/guide_to_startups_part4.html

- Market Business. (2019). What is a refund? Definition and examples.
<https://marketbusinessnews.com/financial-glossary/refund/>
- MaRS Startup Toolkit. (2022). Social enterprise business models.
<https://learn.marsdd.com/article/social-enterprise-business-models/>
- Martic, K. (2019). 20+ Employee Recognition Program Benefits and Ideas. SEMOS Cloud.
<https://semoscloud.com/blog/employee-recognition-program-benefits-ideas/#:~:text=Employee%20recognition%20programs%20are%20employer,some%20employee%20recognition%20program%20ideas.&text=Employee%20recognition%20programs%20have%20many,not%20sure%20where%20to%20start>
- Mike Isaac. (February 22, 2017). Inside Uber's Aggressive, Unrestrained Workplace Culture. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/02/22/technology/uber-workplace-culture.html>.
- Muñoz, P., & Cohen, B. (2017). Mapping out the sharing economy: A configurational approach to sharing business modeling. Technological Forecasting and Social Change
<https://www.hse.ru/data/2018/01/26/1162943204/program-1905868711-QPJ84A4umM.pdf>
- Netflix Marketing Strategy & Marketing Mix (4Ps). (2021). MBA Skool Team.
<https://www.mbaskool.com/marketing-mix/services/17729-netflix.html>
- Nwokike, F. (2021). Who Is An Entrepreneur?. The Total Entrepreneurs for Entrepreneurs and Startups. <https://thetotalentrepreneurs.com/who-is-an-entrepreneur-2/>
- Ong, S. Q. (2022). The ultimate guide to referral marketing. Oberlo.
<https://www.oberlo.com/blog/referral-marketing>
- Osterwalder, A. (2004) The Business Model Ontology-A Proposition in a Design Science Approach. Dissertation 173, University of Lauseanne, Switzerland. Osterwalder, A. (2009) How to Systematically Build Business Models Beyond Profit. [Online] Available from:
<http://www.slideshare.net/Alex.Osterwalder/business-models-beyond-profit-socialentrepreneurship-lecture-wise-etienne-eichenberger-iqbal-quadir-grameen-bank-grameen-phone> [Accessed: 10 May 2021]
- Osterwalder, A. (2010) Combining Business Model Prototyping, Customer Development, and Social Entrepreneurship. [Online] Available from:
<http://businessmodelalchemist.com/blog/2010/08/combining-business-model-prototyping-customerdevelopment-and-social-entrepreneurship.html> [Accessed: 10 May 2021]
- Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers. John Wiley & Sons. (2)R2. Amit, R., & Zott, C. (2001).
- Pincus, A. (June 18, 2007). The perfect (elevator) pitch. Bloomberg Businessweek.
http://www.businessweek.com/careers/content/jun2007/ca20070618_134959.htm "Business Plan vs. PPM vs. Prospectus," Prospectus.com, <https://www.prospectus.com/business-plan-vs-ppm-vs-prospectus/>
- Piotrowicz, W., & Cuthbertson, R. (2014). Introduction to the special issue information technology in retail: Toward omnichannel retailing. International Journal of Electronic Commerce, 18 (4), 5-16.
- Practical guide to doing business in Europe. (n.d.) Your Europe.
https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/finance-funding/getting-funding/access-finance/index_en.htm

- Publications office of the European Union. (n.d.). Social economy and social entrepreneurship. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/cc9e291c-517c-4c64-9f29-428b34aea56d>
- Putter, M. (2021). What is a personal development plan? CPD Online College Knowledge base. <https://cpdonline.co.uk/knowledge-base/business/what-are-personal-development-plans/>
- Questus. (2021). 10 modeli biznesowych, które zrewolucjonizowały świat. <https://questus.pl/blog/10-modeli-biznesowych-ktore-zrewolucjonizowaly-swiat/>
- Reiff, N. (2022). Series A, B, C Funding: How It Works. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/personal-finance/102015/series-b-c-funding-what-it-all-means-and-how-it-works.asp>
- Scott, J. T., (2017). The entrepreneur's guide to building a successful business. EFMD. <https://efmdglobal.org/wp-content/uploads/The-Entrepreneurs-Guide-to-Building-a-Successful-Business-2017.pdf>
- SendPulse. (2022). What is Promotional Marketing: Definition and Tips. <https://sendpulse.com/support/glossary/promotional-marketing>
- Sergio Sparviero (2019) The Case for a Socially Oriented Business Model Canvas: The Social Enterprise Model Canvas, Journal of Social Entrepreneurship, 10:2, 232-251, DOI: 10.1080/19420676.2018.1541011
- Shewan, D. (2022). 7 of the Best Value Proposition Examples We've Ever Seen. WordStream. <https://www.wordstream.com/blog/ws/2016/04/27/value-proposition-examples>
- Smith, G. (2012) The Nonprofit Business Model Canvas | Innovative Nonprofit. [Online] Available from: <http://www.innovativenonprofit.com/2012/08/the-nonprofit-business-model-canvas-2/#.Uzz5ivmSwoy> [Accessed: 20 March 2021]
- Social Business Model Canvas. (2021). Business Model Toolbox. <https://bmtoolbox.net/tools/social-business-model-canvas/>
- Social Business Model Canvas. (2022). Social Business Design. <https://socialbusinessdesign.org/what-is-a-social-business-model-canvas/>
- Social Business Model Canvas. (n.d.). A new Social Business Model Canvas online. <https://socialbusinessmodelcanvas.swarthmore.edu>
- Social Enterprise Institute (2018). Social business model canvas: <https://socialenterpriseinstitute.co/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Social-Business-Model-Canvas.pdf>
- Social Europe. (2013). Social economy and social entrepreneurship. <https://www.euricse.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/social-economy-guide.pdf>
- Social Innovation Lab. (2013). Social Business Model Canvas. [Online] Available from: <http://www.socialbusinessmodelcanvas.com/> [Accessed: 20th March 2021]
- Sorescu, A., Frambach, R. T., Singh, J., Rangaswamy, A., & Bridges, C. (2011). Innovations in retail business models. Journal of Retailing, 87, S3- S16.
- Stacy J. Belinsky and Brian Gogan. (October 2016). "Throwing a Change-Up, Pitching a Strike: An Autoethnography of Frame Acquisition, Application, and Fit in a Pitch Development and Delivery Experience," IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication, 59 no. 4. <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7592403/>

- Startup Business. (2017). Chi è l'intrapreneur e perchè uno startupper può diventarlo. <https://www.startupbusiness.it/intrapreneur-chi-e-e-perche-uno-startupper-puo-diventarlo/90634/>
- Strategy Made Simple (2020). Video: Overview of the Social Business Model Canvas. <https://strategymadesimple.ca/blog/video-overview-of-the-social-business-model-canvas>
- Street Business School. Addressing sustainable development through economic empowerment. (n.d.). https://www.streetbusinessschool.org/blog/economic-empowerment-sustainable-development-goals/?gclid=CjwKCAiAq8f-BRBtEiwAGr3DgaTioHH-YpTE_F2g_fKKwFMDGYUkQ8p24WNfPBDovzr-L9vvN21ebBoCYe4QAvD_BwE
- Sustainable development Goals. UN. <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/>
- Tarver, E. (2021). Social Economics. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-economics.asp>
- The Canvas | Social Lean Canvas. (n.d.). [Online] Available from: <http://socialleancanvas.com/the-canvas/> [Accessed: 10th February 2021]
- The impact gaps canvas. (n.d.). Tackling heropreneurship. <https://tacklingheropreneurship.com/the-impact-gaps-canvas/>
- The Myth of the Elevator Pitch. (n.d.). Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254004669_The_Myth_of_the_Elevator_Pitch [accessed Oct 15 2021].
- Tore, J. J. (2015). Who Is An Entrepreneur?. Entrepreneur middle east. www.entrepreneur.com/article/245628
- Twin, A. (2022). Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/k/kpi.asp>
- UN. (n.d.). Coronavirus: United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.undp.org/coronavirus>
- UNESCO. (n.d.). Education for sustainable development. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-sustainable-development/what-is-esd/sd>
- United Nations. (2015). Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Sustainable development. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld/publication>
- United Nations. (2020). 2020 World Youth Report - United Nations. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/youth/wp-content/uploads/sites/21/2020/07/2020-World-Youth-Report-FULL-FINAL.pdf>
- United Nations. (2020). First Person: COVID-19 is not a silver lining for the climate, says UN Environment chief. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2020/04/1061082>
- University Lab Partners. (2019, August 19). What's the Difference Between an Inventor, Entrepreneur and Innovator?. <https://www.universitylabpartners.org/blog/difference-inventor-entrepreneur-innovator>
- University of Wisconsin sustainable management. (n.d). The Triple Bottom Line. <https://sustain.wisconsin.edu/sustainability/triple-bottom-line/>

- Using the business model canvas for social enterprise design. (n.d). <https://cscuk.fcdo.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/BMC-for-Social-Enterprise.pdf>
- Value creation in e-business. (n.d). *Strategic management journal*, 22(6-7), 493-520.
- Vantage Circle (2022). 50 Rewards And Recognition Ideas To Boost Employee Recognition. <https://blog.vantagecircle.com/rewards-and-recognition-ideas/>
- Wallbridge, A. (2020). How to Write and Manage Personal Development Plans. TSW Training. <https://www.tsw.co.uk/blog/leadership-and-management/personal-development-plan/>
- Whalley, A. (2010). *Strategic Marketing*. Bookboon.com. <https://library.ku.ac.ke/wp-content/downloads/2011/08/Bookboon/Strategy/strategic-marketing.pdf>
- Wirtz, B., Pistoia, A., Ullrich, S., and Göttel, V. (2015). Business models: Origin, development and future research perspectives. *Long Range Planning*, forthcoming:1-19.
- Yildirim, H. (2022). The 5Ps of Marketing – everything you need to know to achieve success. *User Guiding*. <https://userguiding.com/blog/the-5-ps-of-marketing/>
- Your Europe. Access to finance. (2021). https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/finance-funding/getting-funding/access-finance/index_en.htm
- Zott, C., Amit, R., & Massa, L. (2011). The business model: recent developments and future research. *Journal of management*, 37(4), 1019- 1042.

Appendix 1. Evaluation quiz check sheets

1b	14a	27b
2a	15c	28b
3c	16a	29b
4b	17b	30a
5b	18b	31c
6a	19a	32a
7c	20c	33b
8a	21a	34a
9c	22a	35b
10c	23b	36a
11b	24c	37c
12b	25a	38c
13a	26a	